

MAELSTROM

MArInE Litter SusTainable RemOval and Management

D2.3

Ecosystem state and ML
pollution assessment
in the two demo sites
(Lagoon of Venice and
the Porto region)

30/09/2022

MAELSTROM

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Executive Summary

The MAELSTROM project aims to test and evaluate innovative technologies for the removal of marine litter in different coastal environments, also assessing their impact on the ecosystems in chosen demo sites and evaluating the economic and societal benefits of the MAELSTROM solutions within local economies. The purpose of the Deliverable 2.3 is to provide a first survey of the ecological status of demo sites (Venice coastal area and Porto region) before the testing of the cleaning technologies. For the two demo sites, the Deliverable describes the methodologies for the mapping of marine litter and microplastics and the methods used for the evaluation of the state of the biological communities characterising the two areas. The main results of this first environmental assessment are presented as well.

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1 Introduction to the MAELSTROM project

MAELSTROM is a project funded under the Topic CE-FNR-09-2020 Pilot action for the removal of marine plastics and litter. MAELSTROM strives to provide answers and diversified solutions to the complex question to the removal and sustainable treatment of marine litter legacy. MAELSTROM contemplates the integration of complementary technologies for marine litter removal in different European coastal ecosystems, compounded with full-fledged circular economy and societal oriented solutions. In particular, the project (i) sets out a reliable multidisciplinary and scientifically sound approach for the assessment of marine debris distribution and impact on marine life in highly valuable ecosystems and protected areas; (ii) designs and manufactures scalable, replicable and automated technologies, co-powered with renewable energy and second generation fuel, to identify, remove and sort marine litter; (iii) evaluates over time the effectiveness of marine litter removal devices along with their impact on local ecosystems; (iv) integrates different technologies to track, sort and recycle all types of collected marine litter into valuable raw materials for future marketisation; (v) assesses the economic and societal impact of the MAELSTROM solutions providing also a comprehensive life-cycle assessment of the technologies and products; (vi) enhances social awareness about the marine litter issue and engages citizens and stakeholders in MAELSTROM activities; (vii) interplays with similar projects to maximize innovation uptake for marine litter removal within and outside the EU.

MAELSTROM

2 MAELSTROM Consortium

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3 Aim of the Deliverable

The Deliverable 2.3 reports and describes the results obtained in the Task 2.3 - Ecosystem and ML pollution state assessment in the Venice coastal area (IT) before cleaning, and in the Task 2.4 Ecosystem and ML pollution state assessment in the Porto region (PT) before cleaning. This report includes the results of the assessment of ML presence and the state of the biological communities before the starting of the cleaning operations in the two demo sites.

In the Venice area (coastal site and lagoon site), the quantification of seafloor macro-litter was performed through a multibeam echosounder system and through ROV video survey. The ecosystem state was evaluated through the monitoring of macro-zoobenthic and fish communities. The evaluation of microplastics was performed in surface water, sediments and biota (the mussel *Mytilus galloprovincialis* and fish). Lastly, the presence of possible microcontaminants deriving from plastics was evaluated in water samples.

In the Porto region, floating macropastics were quantified through visual monitoring during the ecosystem state assessment, whereas microplastic particles were evaluated in the water column. Water quality and the ecosystem ecological status were determined through the metrics defined by the Water Framework Directive for transitional waters. General physical and chemical parameters, analysis of biological parameters and hydro-morphological elements were also characterized.

4 State-of-the art of the Demo sites

In this section, we intend to give a brief description of the Italian and Portuguese Demo sites, and an overview of the previous information available on the sources of marine litter and microplastics in the two geographical areas.

4.1 State-of-the-art of the Italian demo site

The Gulf of Venice is the northern part of the Adriatic Sea, extending eastward for 95 km from the Po River delta (Italy), to the coast of Istria (Slovenia and Croatia) (Figure 1). The average water depth is about 40 m. The area receives relevant riverine inputs from Po, Adige, Piave, and Tagliamento rivers. Marshes, lagoons and sand littorals characterise the gulf's shores. The Gulf is subject to anthropic pressures such as nutrient loads from agriculture, pollution from coastal towns, fishery, coastal and maritime tourism, traffic from maritime routes.

The lagoon of Venice is located in the northwest part of the Gulf (45° 12' N) and is the largest Mediterranean lagoon (surface 500 km², vertical north-south length 50 km, mean horizontal width 15 km). Three inlets connect the lagoon with the open sea (Lido, Malamocco and Chioggia, from north to south). The bathymetry is characterised by the presence of navigable channels, tidal flats and shoals. Its average depth is approximately 1 m, with only 5% deeper than 5 m (some navigable channels are deeper than 15 m) and 75 % is shallower than 2 m. The Venice Lagoon is a microtidal environment with mean tidal range from 50 cm during neap tide to 100 cm during spring tide. The tidal exchange can reach 20,000 m³ s⁻¹ at peak flow during spring tides (Umgiesser, 2020).

The lagoon of Venice is characterised by various point and non-point sources of pollutant inputs that converge in its basin. These sources are often localized in specific areas, mainly deriving from the industries of the Porto Marghera district, the sewage and urban runoff from the cities of Venice and Chioggia, and the run-off from the drainage basins which are intensively urbanized and cultivated.

Notwithstanding the high anthropogenic impact, the Venice lagoon ecosystem still shows good resilience, providing a broad range of ecosystem services (Rova et al., 2015, 2019).

The entire Venice coastal area is impacted by marine litter in several ways (Pasquini et al., 2016; Liubartseva et al., 2016, Liubartseva et al., 2018). In particular, accumulation of marine litter on the bottom has been showed to be relevant (the western gulf of Venice was shown to be one of the most impacted area in the Adriatic Sea by Fortibuoni et al., 2019).

Fisheries is one main maritime activity and an important economic resource in the area. The combination of an intense fishing activity and the characteristics of the sea bottom (presence of rocky outcrops at sea) make this area exposed to the impact from Abandoned, Lost or otherwise Discarded Fishing Gear (ALDFG). Moreover, the region hosts a number of mussel farms, accounting for nearly the 33% of the national production. Aquaculture, and specifically mussel farming, has been shown to contribute significantly to seafloor litter (Fortibuoni et al., 2019). High presence of mussel nets in the northern and central Adriatic Sea has been already detected by various studies (Strafella et al., 2015; Pasquini et al., 2016; Vlachogianni et al., 2018), even in protected areas (Melli et al., 2017).

The Port of Venice is Italy's eighth largest port in traffic volume terms, and one of the most important in the Mediterranean for cruise ships, catering to an enormous flow of people and vehicles. Maritime traffic has been already recognized as a source for marine litter in the area (Liubartseva et al., 2018).

Figure 1– The Gulf of Venice in the North Adriatic Sea and the Lagoon of Venice.

4.2 State-of-the-art of the Portugal demo site

Located in the northwest of Portugal, the Ave River hydrological basin (Figure 2) has an approximate area of 1390 km². From its source in Serra da Cabreira to its mouth in Vila do Conde the river length is 101 km (Rocha et al., 2019). The Ave River estuarine area is located in the Vila do Conde municipality, in the district of Porto, with an area of 149.03 km² (data in 2013) and with 79 739 inhabitants (data in 2019, mean annual population change = 0.050%), subdivided into 21 parishes (www.pordata.pt). It is a coast municipality, limited at the west by the Atlantic Ocean (Figure 2). The municipality is limited to the north by the municipality of Póvoa de Varzim, to the east by Vila Nova de Famalicão and Trofa and to the south by Maia and Matosinhos.

The Ave River differs from other northern Portuguese rivers not only because of its high pollution levels, but also because of the large spatial and temporal variability of pollutant concentration (Gonçalves and Alpuim, 2011; Rocha et al., 2019). During the last years, several monitoring works have been developed in this river and its estuary to assess the anthropogenic pollution, including emerging contaminants (e.g. Ribeiro et al., 2016; Caetano et al., 2016; Couto et al., 2018, 2019; Rocha et al., 2019).

Overall, the watercourses of the Ave hydrographic basin (Figure 2) present serious disturbances, regarding physical, chemical and biological levels, with few exceptions recorded only in the upstream area close to the springs. These disturbances (Table 1)

are translated into several effects in the ecosystem, namely the degradation of the riparian curtain, the alteration of the channel, and the poor quality of the water. As expected, these disturbances have significant consequences on the aquatic communities. The surrounding area of the Ave estuary is mainly urban, except on the left margin where a small wasteland with a few species of ruderal plants and very low fauna densities can be found (Figure 2).

Figure 2 – Maps of a) the location of the hydrographic basin of the Ave River in Portugal, b) the Ave hydrographic basin land use characterization, and c) the Ave estuary with land use characterization in the surrounding area of the study sites.

Along the hydrographic basin of Ave River, several pressures were identified contributing to the occurrence of litter in the aquatic ecosystem (Figure 2 and Table 1). Regarding the land use and the potential contributions to the aquatic ecosystem degradation, the artificial territories and agriculture are the most significant sources of debris in the Ave River. This is because around 50% of the hydrographic basin is covered by these landcover uses. This area is one of the most industrialized area of Portugal, hosting a huge number of industries (Table 1), such as those of textiles (19

Installations covered by the IPPC regime - Integrated Pollution Prevention and Control) and surface treatment (electrolytic or chemical process; 12 with environmental license-IPPC) (Figure 2 and Table 1), metal plating, leather tanning, rubber and plastic, cutlery and metalworking manufactures (Rocha et al., 2019). These lead to high levels of pollution and to a decrease of water quality that have been registered in this region during the last decades (Couto et al., 2019). Other activities also contribute to the impact of marine litter in the aquatic ecosystem, such as landfills (6 plants: Urban solid waste and Non-hazardous industrial waste), aquaculture plants (5 installations), port facilities (4 ports in the transitional waters area), and tourism. The latter more pronounced in the Ave River estuary due to the urban activities of the fishing town of Vila do Conde, located in the northern margin of the estuarine area.

Table 1 – Land use and pollution sources in the Ave Estuary.

Land use	Area (ha)	Area (%)
1. Artificial territories	28370.2	20.4
2. Agriculture	40243.3	29.0
3. Pastures	496.992	0.36
4. Agroforestry surfaces	0.00001	<0.001
5. Forests	56174.3	40.4
6. Bush and shrubs	12280.6	8.84
7. Open spaces or with little vegetation	848.153	0.61
8. Wetlands	0.0000	0.0
9. Superficial water bodies	506.836	0.37
Pollution sources	Number	%
• Textile industry	19	31.7
• Metallurgical, metalworking, drawing, automobile industry	12	20.0
• Wastewater treatment plants	7	11.7
• Feed industry	7	11.7
• Landfills	6	10.0
• Livestock	4	6.67
• Press/Print shop industry	2	3.33
• Production of electrical cables industry	1	1.67
• Thermal insulation industry	1	1.67
• Mineral industry	1	1.67

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5 Case study: Venice coastal area, Italy

5.1 Ecological assessment in the Venice demo sites

The demo site of the Venice coastal area includes two different areas, one at sea (1. Coastal site) and one inside the lagoon (2. Lagoon site) (Figure 3). Both areas are characterised by historically accumulated marine litter. The identification of the demonstration sites in Venice was based on field surveys, on previous data and information available on ML presence and abundances for the Venice coastal area. The MAELSTROM DoA foresees that specific monitoring activities have to take place in proximity of a mussel farm to assess the state of macro zoo-benthic and fish communities, and on shellfish before the testing of the innovative technology. Consequently, we decided that the Coastal Demo Site should be near a mussel farm concession at sea (where most of the mussel farms are located), whereas the Lagoon Site should be characterised by the presence of urban-derived litter.

An abandoned concession for mussel harvesting was considered as demonstration area. Non-operational concessions have some advantages with respect to active ones for testing innovative technologies: the environment and the sea bottom are characterised by the presence of all the waste deriving from mussel farm activities, but here testing operations can be carried out without interfering with the economic activities of farming. This is also important considering the size of the platform. The attention was focused on an abandoned mussel farm located in front of the Sile river mouth.

As for the Lagoon site, in the framework of the MarGnet Project (Mapping and recycling of marine litter and ghost nets on the sea-floor, EASME/EMFF/2017/1.2.1.12/S2/05/SI2.789314), the area of Sacca Fisola was monitored in the 2019 and a ML hotspot was found. The surveyed area was characterised by the presence of various items such as tires, poles, crates, boats and other items (Madricardo et al., 2020). This area was selected for the MAELSTROM Project.

For more details on the decision process that led to the choice of the two Venice coastal area sites, see the Deliverable 5.1 - Report on site identification and installation of the Seabed Cleaning System in Venice.

Figure 3–Venice coastal area demo sites

The abandoned mussel farm is located in front of the Sile River mouth, at about 1.7 nautical miles from the coast and it has a total surface of 1.960.000 m² (Figure 4). The area has a mean depth of about 14 m. The mussel farm was disused some years ago, but the owner left at sea all the structures used to harvest mussels. A characteristic of this mussel farm is that it hosted an “Experimental field” used in the past for research activities. The area is located about 2 nautical miles off the coast. The “Experimental field” was established in the early 2000s by the Veneto Environmental Agency (ARPAV). The experimental field consists of a rectangular zone with sides of 50 and 100 m for a total extension of 5,000 m². The central coordinates of the area are (WGS84) 45 ° 27.07 'N and 12 ° 35.47' E. In the area, artificial structures were installed with the aim of facilitating the establishment of hard bottom communities, to attract fish and to allow the growth of mussels within long-lines. The introduction of artificial hard substrates in an environment characterised by a soft bottom aimed to fill the knowledge gaps related to the realisation of submerged artificial reefs in the Venetian coast. In the area a series of multidisciplinary studies were carried out in the past, consequently many historical data are available as reference.

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The presence of the “Experimental field” within the abandoned mussel farm has a series of significant advantages: it allows to study the possible impact of the MAELSTROM innovative solution (i.e. the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform) not only on soft substrate biological communities both also on the hard substrate of the pyramids. Moreover, previous data on biological communities on the area are available from previous research that can be used as background for the ecological assessment.

In agreement with the MAELSTROM team that is developing the technology and with the Coast Guard, it has been decided that the Seabed Cleaning Platform will be operating in an area corresponding to about 2% of the total area of the mussel farm, corresponding to a surface of about 40.000 m². This area comprises also the “Experimental field” to allow sampling also on hard substrate.

Figure 4 – Venice Lagoon demo site 1: coastal site – abandoned mussel farm (source ARPAV 2010).

Sacca Fisola Island is located along the Giudecca Canal, southeast of the historical centre of Venice (Figure 5). It is an artificial island, created in the 1960s. From 1969 to 1984 Sacca San Biagio, another small artificial island connected to Sacca Fisola, housed an incinerator for municipal solid waste. The area still hosts the Veritas (the Venice waste management company) worksite, where waste is delivered daily.

The sampling area is located in a minor navigation channel (few m deep), mainly used by boats for transportation of goods and by residents and also by the vessels of the Venetian Waste Management Authority (Veritas) to deliver waste.

Figure 5 – Venice Lagoon demo site 2: Lagoon site - Sacca Fisola. Bathymetry and marine litter items detected. (Source Madricardo et al.2020).

Given the objectives of Task 2.3, an integrated framework has been defined to assess the status of marine ecosystems in the demo site of the lagoon of Venice, including the state of contamination from macro- and micro-litter. The framework is illustrated in Figure 6. Seafloor mapping is used to assess macro-litter presence on the seabottom. Waters and sediments are characterised for the presence of microplastics and microcontaminants. Community state and content of microplastics are assessed for some biological compartments, namely macrozoobenthos and fish.

Ecosystem state and ML pollution assessment: Venice demo sites

Figure 6 – Integrated assessment framework defined to study the Venice demo site

5.2 Methodologies

5.2.1 Mapping of the study areas

The mapping of the Lagoon and Coastal Site in the Venice coastal area was done thanks to underwater acoustic high resolution remote sensing by mean of multibeam echosounder surveys aimed at identifying macrolitter items. Video inspections with a mini-ROV equipped with a small camera were then carried out to ground truth the interpretation of the targets identified analyzing the underwater acoustic data collected.

5.2.1.1 Multibeam Echosounder data acquisition

The same instrumental set up was used during the two multibeam surveys carried out respectively at Sacca Fisola in October 2021 and at the abandoned mussel farm in February 2022. The only exception was the multibeam systems, which anyway belonged to the same product's family and guaranteed the same data quality.

The multibeam echo sounder (MBES) was pole-mounted on the CNR research vessel Litus, a 11-m-long boat with 1.5-m-deep draft. The acquisition system is furnished with a Seapath 380 system, supplied by Real Time Kinematic (RTK) online corrections and integrated with the Kongsberg motion sensor MRU 5 and with a Dual Antenna GPS, that allow to take in account for ship positioning and for pitch, roll, heave and yaw movements, Figure 7.

The system was completed by a Valeport mini SVS sensor, attached close to the transducer to continuously measure the sound velocity for the beamforming. Sound velocity profiles (SVPs) were collected with an AML oceanographic Smart-X sound velocity profiler every day at the beginning of the activities or whenever the temperature and salinity of the water changed significantly, as the tidal phases changed. Data was logged, displayed and checked in real-time by the Kongsberg data acquisition and control software SIS (Seafloor Information System).

The processing of the acquired data was carried out using the Caris HIPS & SIPS 11 software following the standard procedures for data conversion, tide correction (tide data provided by ISPRA, referred to the ZMPS 1897), creation of surfaces, cleaning of spurious data and application of refraction coefficients for the correction of speed of sound errors.

The bathymetric data processed in Caris HIPS and SIPS were imported into ARCGIS for further analysis.

Figure 7. Litus Vessel and MBES system

At the Venice coastal area (the abandoned mussel farm), the survey was performed with a Kongsberg EM-2040c compact single head multi-frequency multibeam system (MBES), 400 beams per swath, 1° beamwidth at 400 KHz. An operational frequency of 320 KHz was chosen.

The survey was carried out from 8 to 10 February 2022, following transects parallel to the coast (Figure 8). A total of 120 lines was done for 116 km of navigation. The Mussel Farm surface extends for 2.2 km². The “Experimental field” area, totally inside the farm area, accounts for 0.15 km². The seafloor is almost flat, with a mean depth around -14 m (Figure 9).

Water column backscatter intensity data were collected as well to identify the presence of suspended items in the water column.

Figure 8 - Survey lines at the abandoned mussel farm.

Figure 9 - Bathymetry of the area within the abandoned mussel farm with the zoom-in showing the Experimental field.

At Sacca Fisola, survey data were collected with a Kongsberg EM-2040p compact single head multi-frequency multibeam system (MBES), 512 beams per swath, 1° beamwidth at 400 KHz. Also in this case, the operational frequency was set to 320 KHz.

The survey took place on the 21st of October 2021. Twelve navigation lines (about 7.2 km, Figure 10) were necessary to cover the area (about 0.024 Km²). Bathymetry ranges between 1 to 7 meters, Figure 11.

Figure 10 - Surveyed lines of Sacca Fisola.

Figure 11 - Bathymetry of Sacca Fisola.

5.2.1.2 Video inspection

After the first ML abundance estimate made with the analysis of the bathymetric data, video inspections were performed with a mini-ROV in the two target areas to validate and confirm what was identified through MBES data analyses. The ROV was cable-controlled and was equipped with a high-resolution camera. ROV surveys took place in the two study sites on the 16th and 17th of June 2022. The mini-ROV was equipped with a high-resolution camera and connected by a cable which was remotely controlled on-board (Figure 12). It was navigated as close as possible to the seabed or objects for at least five minutes to collect videos in the target areas. However, the accurate location of the videos are unknown because the available mini-ROV was without a positioning system. Therefore, a buffer of 10 m was set as an estimation of the possible location of the video observations, which was based on the maximum cable out of the ROV during the survey.

Figure 12 – mini-ROV with high-resolution camera.

5.2.2 Assessment of the biological community

5.2.2.1 Macro-zoobenthos assessment

Soft bottom macrozoobenthic communities were characterized both in the marine and lagoon sites. At the marine site, hard bottom communities on artificial substrate were characterized as well by a non-destructive approach (photoquadrats). The marine site includes the so-called “Experimental field”, which from 2003 to 2010 was used in the framework of research programs dedicated to various components of the ecosystem, including soft bottom and artificial hard substrate macrozoobenthos, the latter being investigated through both destructive and non-destructive sampling practices (ARPAV, 2006; Da Ros et al., 2010).

5.2.2.1.1 Soft bottom macrobenthos

The same protocol was applied on both marine and lagoon soft bottom macrobenthos. The protocol includes sampling by grabs on two stations (three

replicates for each station), taxonomic determination and quantitative analysis of the community matrix. On both sites, a third additional station was sampled. This sample will be analyzed only if more information about benthic communities is needed.

The sampling procedure overall follows the approach foreseen by the Marine Strategy Framework Directive protocols implemented in Italy (MATTM, 2018). Quantitative benthic samples were collected with a Van Veen grab having a surface area of 0.1 m² and a volume of approximately 17 l (Figure 13). Sampled sediment volume was required to be greater than 50% or 75% of the grab capacity, respectively for sandy and muddy sediments. The collected sediment was transferred to numbered buckets. Field information was recorded on data sheets. In laboratory, samples were immediately sieved at 1 mm mesh size, gently washing them with filtered sea water. The retained material, including macrobenthic organisms, shell detritus and other residual material, was stored in 70% ethanol.

Figure 13 – The Van Veen grab used for sampling activities

The geographical position of sampling stations was planned in advance on the basis of relevant environmental information at the study scale (mainly bathymetric and backscatter data collected by preliminary MBES surveys carried out respectively on February 2022 in the area of the coastal marine site and October 2021 in the area of the lagoon site, see the previous chapter for more details), as well as the planned location of cleaning activities over the study areas. The sampling design is aimed at

including locations interested (impact) or not (reference) by cleaning activities, reducing other environmental sources of variation.

At the marine site, sampling was carried out on board the vessel M/B Litus of CNR-ISMAR Venice on 3/03/2022 in the immediate proximity of the chosen stations, respectively CS1 (on the planned cleaning area), CS2 (reference) and CS3 (additional) (see Figure 14 and Table 2). Sampling point positions were recorded with the vessel GPS.

Figure 14 – Map of sampling stations in the Coastal site; the “Experimental field” and hard substrate stations are also showed.

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Table 2 – Geographic coordinates (WGS84) of sampling points: planned coordinates of CS1 (on the planned cleaning area), CS2 (control) and CS3 (additional) and position of replicates A, B, C recorded in field.

Station	Replicate	Latitude	Longitude	Depth (m)
CS1	Station planned	45°27.056' N	12°35.631' E	
CS1	A	45°27.059' N	12°35.625' E	14.8
CS1	B	45°27.057' N	12°35.629' E	14.8
CS1	C	45°27.065' N	12°35.633' E	14.8
CS2	Station planned	45°27.126' N	12°35.582' E	
CS2	A	45°27.125' N	12°35.580' E	14.6
CS2	B	45°27.127' N	12°35.582' E	14.6
CS2	C	45°27.127' N	12°35.582' E	14.6
CS3	Station planned	45°27.046' N	12°35.678' E	
CS3	A	45°27.051' N	12°35.665' E	14.9
CS3	B	45°27.051' N	12°35.675' E	14.9
CS3	C	45°27.049' N	12°35.677' E	14.9

At the lagoon site, sampling was carried out on board the M/B Litus of CNR-ISMAR Venice on 1/04/2022 in the immediate proximity of the planned stations, respectively LV1 (on the planned cleaning area), LV2 (reference) and LV3 (additional) (see Figure 15 and Table 3). Sampling point positions were recorded with the vessel GPS.

Figure 15 – Map of sampling stations in the Lagoon site.

Table 3 – Geographic coordinates (WGS84) of sampling points: planned coordinates of LV1 (on the planned cleaning area), LV2 (control) and LV3 (additional) and position of replicates A, B, C recorded in field.

Station	Replicate	Latitude	Longitude	Depth (m)
LV1	Station planned	45°25.506' N	12°18.619' E	
LV1	A	45°25.509' N	12°18.617' E	4.7
LV1	B	45°25.508' N	12°18.609' E	4.2
LV1	C	45°25.510' N	12°18.612' E	4.7
LV2	Station planned	45°25.491' N	12°18.794' E	
LV2	A	45°25.491' N	12°18.794' E	4.6
LV2	B	45°25.491' N	12°18.792' E	4.7
LV2	C	45°25.492' N	12°18.792' E	4.6
LV3	Station planned	45°25.563' N	12°18.451' E	
LV3	A	45°25.564' N	12°18.447' E	5.1
LV3	B	45°25.563' N	12°18.455' E	5.1
LV3	C	45°25.565' N	12°18.452' E	5.2

The analysis of the samples followed consolidated procedures (Gambi & Dappiano, 2003). Samples were treated with rose bengal dye and sorted by means of a binocular stereoscope (6.4x - 40x). All macrozoobenthos was separated from the matrix and divided into homogeneous taxonomic groups (phylum or class) and kept in a 70% ethanol solution. All the specimens were identified using main taxonomic keys available for the different groups and counted. The determination was carried out at the species level or at the highest possible resolution, in that case open nomenclature rules were applied (Sigovini et al., 2016). The World Register of Marine Species (<https://www.marinespecies.org>, updated on 27/04/2022) was used as taxonomic reference.

Data were organized as abundance matrix (Annex 1). Community structure was described by main univariate ecological descriptors as well as multivariate analyses. Selected univariate descriptors include abundance, richness, diversity indices and associated metrics, biotic and multimetric indices, as listed hereafter:

- abundance, N
- density, N/m²
- species richness, S
- Margalef index, $d = (S-1)/\ln(N)$ (Margalef, 1958). The index have been introduced to make richness independent of the sample size.
- Shannon index, $H' = -\sum_i p_i \log_2 p_i$ ($p_i = n_i/N$, with n_i being the i -th taxon abundance; Shannon & Weaver, 1949). It expresses the "uncertainty" in predicting which species a randomly selected individual belongs to, with values ranging between 0 and ∞ . Like the other diversity indices, it takes into account the richness and distribution of abundances among taxa. A high sample size is assumed ($N \rightarrow \infty$).
- Pielou evenness, $J' = H' / \log_2 S$ (Pielou, 1966). It quantifies the evenness in the distribution of abundances between taxa, with values ranging between 0 and 1.
- AMBI biotic index (Borja et al., 2000). Biotic indices are based on the paradigm that the taxonomic composition is affected by the quality of the system, in terms of the quantitative ratio (abundances) between sensitive and tolerant species, following the theoretical models by Pearson & Rosenberg (1978), Glémarec & Hily (1981) and other previous authors focusing on the organic enrichment of the sediments (see also Tagliapietra et al., 2012). However, biotic indices have been also applied to other types of impacts. Calculation steps are the following: 1) taxa are attributed to one of five "ecological groups" describing the taxon sensitivity, based on lists of species (December 2020 version,

<https://ambi.azti.es/>; if the taxon is missing, a class has been assigned when possible based on expert opinion); 2) a biotic coefficient ranging between 1 and 6 is calculated according to the formula: $BC = (0 \times \%GI) + (1.5 \times \%GII) + (3 \times \%GIII) + (4.5 \times \%GIV) + (6 \times \%GV)$ (GI-GV are the percentage abundances of the five ecological groups; 7 is given in case of azoic samples); 3) a discrete biotic index BI 1-7 may be attributed according to reference BC intervals, however it has not been applied in the present analysis.

- M-AMBI multimetric index (Bald et al., 2005; Muxika et al., 2007). The index integrates S, H' and BC through complex multivariate calculations, however it has been demonstrated that it approximates the simple mean of normalised metrics (Sigovini et al. 2013), with 0-1 normalisation calculated over the following range: a minimum value corresponding to theoretical conditions (S = 0, H' = 0, BC = 6) and a maximum value corresponding either to given high-quality reference conditions (which generally differ according to the monitored environment) or to the highest values in the dataset (the lowest in the case of BC), the latter being applied in the present analysis (calculated from the whole dataset of marine and lagoon community data). The M-AMBI index therefore assumes values between 0 and 1 (or slightly higher than 1).

Of all the indices, only AMBI is independent of the sampled surface, since it does not include richness in the calculation. Therefore, it is not possible a direct comparison of the results with studies where a different surface of sediment have been sampled. Indices were calculated on replicates (and then mean is calculated) as well as stations in order to express this dependence on sample size.

The multivariate community structure of replicates has been explored through well established methods. No data transformation before the analyses was deemed necessary. Agglomerative hierarchical clustering was performed, based on Bray-Curtis similarity index. The group average linkage was applied, which evaluates the similarities between the two groups based on the average similarity between all the pairs of objects within the groups. The results have been represented by means of dendrograms.

NMDS (non-metric Multidimensional Scaling; Shepard, 1962) ordination was also performed, which considers the rank of (dis-) similarity between samples, and projects the stations into a space with reduced dimensions (usually two-dimensional) through an iterative procedure that minimizes a stress function (considered a measure of the "goodness" of the representation).

To test differences in multivariate community composition between stations, two non parametric multivariate approaches were applied: Analysis of similarities (ANOSIM, Clarke, 1993), which compare the compositional dissimilarities between the groups to those within the groups and is performed on the rank order of dissimilarity values (a statistic R, comparable to a correlation coefficient, is produced which ranges between -1 and +1, zero indicating completely random grouping); Permutational multivariate analysis of variance using distance matrices (ADONIS2, Oksanen et al., 2022), which is based on the principles of PERMANOVA (McArdle & Anderson, 2001), and arguably represents a more robust alternative to ANOSIM. Finally, the community composition has been described in terms of main taxonomic groups (at the phylum or class level).

All the analyses were performed with the free and open source R software environment (versione 4.1.2; R Development Core Team, 2021; <http://www.r-project.org/>).

5.2.2.12 *Hard substrate macrobenthos*

The evaluation of hard substrate macrobenthos community was performed only at the coastal marine site. To characterize and monitoring hard bottom benthic communities on the marine site, a non-destructive sampling procedure based on photoquadrats was chosen. Two stations were selected, corresponding to two artificial reef in the “Experimental field”, the “south pyramid” and the “north pyramid” (see Figure 14 and Table 4). Each pyramid is made up of 5 concrete blocks 2x2x2 m arranged as in Figure 16. For each station, photoquadrats were acquired on different surfaces of the pyramid: on the vertical south-east face of a lower block and of the upper one (face N ° 1 and 2) and on the upper block top (face N ° 3). For each face, three replicates (A, B, C) were acquired. Photoquadrats were also acquired on additional surfaces as described below. Finally, an isolated concrete block (2x2x0.8 meters, a former buoy anchor), was also sampled as a third station (see Figure 14 and Table 4). These supernumerary samples were acquired in order to have more information about benthic communities if needed during the course of the project.

Figure 16 – Scheme of the pyramids in the “Experimental field” and position of the photoquadrats.

Table 4 – Geographic coordinates (WGS84) of the underwater structures sampled for the assesment of hard bottom benthic communities.

Station	Latitude	Longitude
North pyramid	45°27.079' N	012°35.558' E
South pyramid	45°27.070' N	012°35.564' E
Isolated block	45°27.047' N	012°35.682' E

Photoquadrats were acquired by positioning on the substrate a metal frame 50x50 cm, divided into 4 sectors. To obtain images with a quality suitable for taxonomic identification of the benthic community (in particular to avoid issues due to turbidity or suspended particles) four close-up images for each frame were acquired, corresponding to the four sectors. The images were captured with high resolution underwater cameras (GoPRO Hero8 and OLYMPUS100).

Sampling was carried out by the Coast Guard diving team on 21-22/03/2022. On both days, two teams of two divers each took part in the activities. Strong currents increased the difficulty of the operations. The first day the visibility was very good, up to 5 meters. During the first day the photoquadrats on faces N ° 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 of the north pyramid were acquired. The following day the visibility was very low, around 1.5 meters. During this day photoquadrats were acquired on the south pyramid (faces N ° 1, 2, 3, 4 and 6) and on the single block (on the north and south vertical face, labelled respectively MN and MS, and on the top, MC). Due to the low height of the block (about

80 cm), and to avoid sediment resuspension, just one replicate on the vertical faces was acquired.

The images were processed by rectifying and creating orthophoto mosaics of the four photos of each photoquadrat (example in Figure 17; all orthomosaics are presented in Annex 2) using the QGIS open source software (QGIS Development Team, 2022), applying a procedure developed for the assessments of the benthic community of biogenic outcrops on the Venetian coast (Tagliapietra et al., 2014) and also applied on the archaeological structures present in the Lagoon of Venice (Guarneri et al., 2022a, b).

Figure 17 – Orthophoto mosaic of photoquadrat 1A, North pyramid; size is 50x50 cm.

Taxonomic identification was performed on the whole 50x50 cm image. All the taxa were identified using available photographic atlases of Mediterranean marine fauna (eg. Trainito & Baldaconi, 2014) as well as main taxonomic keys for the different groups. The determination was carried out at the highest possible resolution, in that case open nomenclature rules were applied (Sigovini et al., 2016, Horton et al., 2021). The World Register of Marine Species (<https://www.marinespecies.org>, updated on 27/04/2022) was used as taxonomic reference. A list of taxa was produced for each photoquadrat. In the subsequent phases, quantitative community data will be produced by estimation of percentage cover, in order to characterize and compare the community structure.

5.2.2.2 Fish community

Fish fauna sampling activities were carried out both at the coastal site (mussel farm) and at the lagoon site (Sacca Fisola) in collaboration with professional fishermen, using different types of nets for the two environments (sea and lagoon).

The use of fishing nets was preferred to visual census sampling methodology to optimise the sampling effort and to adopt the most effective sampling tool also for the future monitoring campaigns. This method allows to obtain comparable results overcoming the potential issue related to the high turbidity that often characterises both the coastal and lagoon areas. It is well known that turbidity is a parameter that could affect the results of the visual census methodology. On the other hand, the use of fishing nets is a widely used method to monitor fish community in these environments (CVN, study B.6.85 and B.6.85/II, Fiorin et al., 2008; Riccato et al., 2008).

In the coastal site (i.e. the mussel farm) different types of nets were employed in order to sample a wide range of ecological and size fish guilds. In particular, four sets of similar nets, each one consisting of a small trap and three 50 meters long nets (33 mm trammel net; 40 mm gillnet; 50 mm gillnet) were displaced in 4 different stations within the sampling area (Figure 18 and Table 5). Given the presence on the bottom of numerous objects (such as the mooring blocks used to anchor the structures of the mussel farm), the nets were placed in neighbouring areas with few or no obstacles in order to preserve the integrity of the nets and to conduct the sampling successfully. The reduced distance from the sampling area was considered suitable to provide a reliable picture of both benthic and pelagic fish species characterising the area. Sampling activities were carried out on February 22-23, 2022 (Figure 19).

Figure 18 – (A) Satellite image showing the sampling stations in the coastal site, (B) Details of the sampling area.

Table 5 – Coordinates of fish fauna sampling stations in the coastal site

Sampling stations	Latitude	Longitude
S1	45°27.106'	12°35.544'
S2	45°27.012'	12°35.475'
S3	45°26.991'	12°35.661'
S4	45°27.085'	12°35.725'

Figure 19 – Fish sampling activities in the coastal site.

Fish were identified according to their species. Moreover, the main morphometric parameters (length and weight) of each individual were recorded.

Fish fauna sampling in the lagoon site was performed using particular fishing gear (fyke nets), locally used in the lagoon, positioned on the seabed of the shallow waters (maximum depth 1.8 meters). Each fishing gear consists of a 130-140-cm-high net barrier ("tressa"), having a minimum mesh size of 14 mm and a variable length, connected to a series of fyke nets ("bertovelli"). The gear was fixed to the seabed with

poles. Ten fyke nets were placed within the sampling site close to the area where removal activities will take place (Figure 20 and Table 6).

Figure 20 – (A) Satellite image showing the removal activity area in the lagoon site, (B) Details of the fish fauna sampling area

Table 6 – Coordinates of fish fauna sampling area in the lagoon site

Vertices coordinates	Latitude	Longitude
S1	45° 25,46748'	12° 18.59928'
S2	45° 25,48974'	12° 18.6144'
S3	45° 25,53156'	12° 18.47724'
S4	45° 25.50822'	12° 18.46206'

Sampling activities were carried out on March 20-22, 2022 (Figure 21). Fish were divided according to their species and the weight was recorded for each individual. Abundance (number of individuals) and biomass (grams) were then standardized per effort unit (number and grams per fyke net and day of fishing).

Figure 21 – Fish sampling activities in the lagoon site

The data collected in both coastal and lagoon sites (number of individuals, species) were used to calculate three biodiversity indexes: species richness, Margalef index and Shannon index.

5.2.3 Microplastic assessment

Microplastic assessment were performed on surface waters, sediments and biota (mussels and fish) in the Venice Demo sites (within the Lagoon and at sea), and in the surface waters in the Porto region Demo site.

As for the quantification of microplastic particles in biota, the mussel *Mytilus galloprovincialis* was chosen due to its filter feeding behaviour and because this species, due to its high tolerance to a wide range of environmental parameters, is widespread in marine as well as in the lagoon environment. Different species of fish were used to analyse the microplastic in their visceral tract, according to their presence and abundance in the coastal area and in the lagoon site.

5.2.3.1 Microplastics assessment in surface waters

Floating microplastics were collected using a Manta trawl with a 330- μ m mesh net and a 0.6 \times 0.3-m rectangular net opening (Figure 22). In each sampling site 3 replicates were performed. Samplings were always carried out in calm conditions, with wind speed not exceeding 2 on the Beaufort wind force scale, since with stronger winds, the rough conditions prevent reliable sample collection on the sea surface. During sampling, the Manta trawl was lowered from the vessel taking care to position it outside the boat's wake and was maintained in flotation for 20 min with a boat speed of 1-3 knots. The Manta trawl was provided with a flowmeter to calculate the volume of water passing through the net. After each sampling, the Manta net was thoroughly

washed to collect all the debris particles stuck to the mesh and samples were transferred into 1-L glass jars. During sample transport and processing, precautions were taken to avoid sample contamination: only glass and metal (preferably stainless steel) tools, cotton coats, and nitrile gloves were used.

Figure 22 – Manta trawl during sampling operation.

Once in laboratory, samples were thoroughly shaken to facilitate detachment of the microplastics from the walls of the 1-L glass container and then filtered through two metal sieves, 5 mm and 300 μm mesh-size, rinsing the glass container several times with filtered sea water (31 μm). The fraction retained by the 5 mm sieve, mainly consisting of plant debris and large planktonic organisms, was thoroughly washed with filtered seawater to remove any adhering microplastics. The obtained fraction, i.e. floating plastic fragments and the few that precipitated (with a density higher than 1.2 g cm^{-3}) were then sorted by microscopic inspection. Microplastic particles were then counted and classified according to color (white, black, red, blue, clear, green, and other colors) and shape (films, fibers, flat fragments, irregular fragments, granules, pellets, and spheres). The results were expressed as the number of particles per cubic meters (Vianello et al., 2018).

5.2.3.2 Microplastic assessment in sediments

Five replicate samples of superficial sediments (0-5 cm) were collected in each sampling site using a Van Veen grab. After collection, they were kept on board in the dark and refrigerated, and rapidly transferred to the laboratory, where all analyses were performed. Microplastics were extracted from each bulk sediment replicate through the density separation according to Frias et al. (2018). The top 5 cm of sediment was collected using a metal spoon and then store in 1-L glass container.

For each replicate sample 250 g (w.w) of sediment was homogenized using a metal spoon and treated with 100 ml of 6-10% hydrogen peroxide. The samples were re-homogenized for at least 1 min and then maintained at room temperature for 18-24 hours. The samples were then washed with filtered water and the microplastic particles were extracted from sediments by density separation procedure. Briefly, 750 ml of NaCl filtered hypersaline solution was added to each sample. The samples were stirred for at least one minute and then left to settle for 1 hour. The supernatant containing the microplastic particles was then filtered using a 38 µm steel sieve. For each replicate sample the extraction procedure was repeated three consecutive times to allow a more effective separation of the microplastics. The three extracted fractions were finally resuspended in Milli-Q water and observed at stereomicroscope. The microplastic particles were then counted and classified according to color (white, black, red, blue, clear, green, and other colors) and shape (films, fibers, flat fragments, irregular fragments, granules, pellets, and spheres). The results were expressed as the number of particles per Kg of sediment.

After particles extraction, an aliquot of sediment replicates was analysed for the determination of granulometry. Sediment samples were dried at 60° C and then mechanically disaggregated with a mortar and pestle. They were then dry sieved using a vibrating sieve with sieve stacks of 355, 500, 710 and 1000 µm to separate the coarser fractions. The individual fractions were then weighed to relate them to the total weight of the sample. The finer fraction (<355 µm) was diluted in 100 ml of distilled water and sonicated before being analyzed using a laser granulometer (LISST-100X, Sequoia Scientific, Inc.), which discretizes the particle size spectrum into 32 classes ranging from 1.90 µm to 381 µm. The concentration values thus obtained were processed and integrated with the data obtained from the sieves. The main statistical parameters of the distribution and the relative abundances (%) of the sand, silt and clay fractions based on the classification of Udden (1914) and Wentworth (1922) were obtained using the GRADISTAT software (Blott & Pye, 2001).

5.2.3.3 Microplastic assessment in biota

Microplastic determinations in the biota have required a preliminary review of the most used protocols for tissue digestion and MP extraction. Starting from the procedure reported by Bour et al. (2018), we carried out numerous preliminary tests to verify if it could be applied to our mussel samples. Briefly, soft tissues of mussels were digested in 10% KOH at 50°C overnight. The amount of KOH to be added was three times the volume of the biological material. After digestion, 100-250 ml of filtered

hypersaline NaCl solution (d 1.2 g / cm³) was added to each sample, supplemented with NaCl to compensate for the dilution related to the sample. The samples were then stirred for 10 min, allowed to settle for a further 10 min and then the supernatant was collected. The separation procedure was performed twice and the total supernatant was filtered using a vacuum pump on a sterile cellulose membrane (5 μ m pore size). Unfortunately, our extracts resulted too dense to be effectively filtered. Consequently, further tests were carried out to verify the effectiveness of another digestive agent (H₂O₂) and higher digestion temperature (65°C), according to the procedure reported in Masià et al (2022). Also in this case, the results were not satisfactory as the procedure did not include an extraction phase and the whole digested and diluted samples continued to present problems in the filtration phase.

Therefore, other tests were performed using KOH as digestive agent and carrying out a longer digestive phase (48h) as reported by Vital et al. (2021) with slight modifications. A sample of 10 mussels from the two pilot sites were frozen and kept at -20 ° C until the time of analysis. The organisms were measured, and the soft tissues of each individual were weighed and individually exposed to the digestion and extraction procedures. In particular, a solution of 10% KOH (1:5 weight:volume) was added to each sample and placed in an oven at 50 °C for 48 h to digest the tissues. After cooling, 100 ml of a NaCl hypersaline solution (1.2 g/cm³) was added to each sample to separate the microplastics present in solution. The mixture was vigorously shaken, introduced in a 500 ml separating funnels and allowed to settle for 24 hours. The supernatant was collected and filtered through 5.0 μ m PVDF porosity filters which were then observed through a stereo microscope (Leica S9D) and MPs quantified and sorted according to their color and shape.

The preliminary results obtained for a small number of individuals for each site (n=3) were considered satisfactory and they were presented in the Result Section, although they needed to be further validated using a higher number of individuals.

The problems of fine-tuning of the digestion phases and extraction methods have consequently slowed down the MP analyses on the biota. Therefore, the completion of the analyses on molluscs and the determination of microplastics in the digestive tracts of fish will be carried out in the next months and the updated results will be presented in Deliverable 2.4 Impact assessment report in the two demo sites (Lagoon of Venice and the Porto region).

5.2.4 Micro-contaminant evaluation in the water column

Two integrated water samples were analysed, one collected in the coastal site and the second in the Lagoon site. A targeted analysis of Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs), Semi-Volatile Organic Compounds (SVOCs) and Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs) was performed via gas-chromatography (GC) with a Mass Spectrometry detector (GC-MS) or a Flame Ionization Detector (GC-FID). The tested chemical classes were aromatic solvents (21 analytes belonging to this class were analysed according to the method APAT CNR IRSA 5140 Man 29 2003. This method makes use of a Purge and Trap procedure to extract the analytes from the water matrix, chlorinated solvents (21 analytes belonging to this class were analysed according to the method APAT CNR IRSA 5150 Man 29 2003). Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (23 analytes belonging to this class were analysed according to the method APAT CNR IRSA 5080 Man 29 2003 extracting the analytes from the water matrix with a liquid-liquid extraction. Aliphatic Hydrocarbons C5-C8 were analysed according to the method APAT CNR IRSA 5140 Man 29 2003 and Hydrocarbons C10-C40 were analysed according to the method UNI EN ISO 9377-2:2002.

5.3 Results

5.3.1 Mapping of the study area

5.3.1.1 Bathymetric data

At the abandoned mussel farm, bathymetric data were visually analyzed using ARCGIS. Different wastes deriving from aquaculture activities could be identified. Particularly, focusing mainly on the “Experimental field”, many mooring blocks, the scours of the ropes and/or chains are well visible on the seafloor. Furthermore, an inspection of water column multibeam echosounder data was performed by using QPS FMMidwater. This inspection allowed to identify the presence of several floating buoys showing a strong backscatter signal in the water column. Figure 23 synthesizes the inspection activity made with ARCGIS and QPS FMMidwater. In Figure 23, a map of detected objects is presented, where the pyramids of the “Experimental field” are clearly visible as well. The coordinates of the mooring blocks and buoys detected within the mapped area are listed in Table 7. The estimated length of the ropes detected within the mapped area is listed in Table 8. The analysis of the video frames that were collected helped to better determine the typology of some objects.

Figure 23 - Map of items detected in the mapped area within the mussel farm with the black squares indicating the mooring blocks, the red diamonds the floating buoys, the black

diamonds the possible floating buoys and the dashed grey lines indicate the position of the rope scours.

Table 7 - List of coordinates of the mooring blocks and buoys detected in the mapped area within the mussel farm.

Item type	Longitude	Latitude
Mooring block	12.59122	45.45247
Mooring block	12.59173	45.45230
Mooring block	12.59378	45.45267
Mooring block	12.59344	45.45225
Mooring block	12.59347	45.45194
Mooring block	12.59335	45.45173
Mooring block	12.59376	45.45187
Mooring block	12.59293	45.45158
Mooring block	12.59266	45.45145
Mooring block	12.59190	45.45127
Mooring block	12.59230	45.45129
Mooring block	12.59213	45.45086
Mooring block	12.59191	45.45096
Mooring block	12.59251	45.45101
Mooring block	12.59228	45.45107
Mooring block	12.59293	45.45110
Mooring block	12.59332	45.45112
Mooring block	12.59390	45.45141
Mooring block	12.59422	45.45147
Mooring block	12.59447	45.45160
Mooring block	12.59424	45.45176
Mooring block	12.59409	45.45196
Mooring block	12.59485	45.45130
Mooring block	12.59571	45.45077
Mooring block	12.59543	45.45036
Mooring block	12.59592	45.45026
Mooring block	12.59469	45.45078
Mooring block	12.59254	45.45048
Mooring block	12.59211	45.44992
Mooring block	12.59107	45.45119
Mooring block	12.59117	45.45153
Mooring block	12.59143	45.45189
Mooring block	12.59583	45.45267

Mooring block	12.59494	45.45227
Floating Buoy at depth -6.9 m	12.59593	45.45026
Floating Buoy at depth -8.9 m	12.59548	45.45037
Floating Buoy at depth -10 m	12.5957	45.45077
Floating Buoy at depth -11 m	12.59214	45.44993
Floating Buoy at depth -9.5 m	12.59473	45.4508
Floating Buoy at depth -9.1 m	12.59249	45.45046
Floating Buoy at depth -5.3 m	12.5919	45.4512
Floating Buoy at depth -10.2 m	12.59144	45.4519
Floating Buoy at depth -9.5 m	12.59171	45.4523
Floating Buoy at depth -9.4 m	12.59172	45.45231
Possible Buoy at depth -7.0 m	12.59084	45.45062
Possible Buoy at depth -7.4 m	12.59229	45.45083
Possible Buoy at depth -7 m	12.59299	45.45099
Possible Buoy at depth -10.2 m	12.59561	45.45186
Possible Buoy at depth -7.7 m	12.59285	45.45128
Possible Buoy at depth -2.8 m	12.59465	45.45051
Possible Buoy at depth -4.4 m	12.59307	45.45161
Possible Buoy at depth -8.6 m	12.59185	45.45244
Possible Buoy at depth -11.5 m	12.59213	45.45243

Table 8 - List of ropes detected in the mapped area within the mussel farm with their estimated length.

Item	Estimated Length (m)
Rope	82
Rope	164
Rope	123
Rope	19
Rope	177
Rope	193
Rope	78
Rope	36
Rope	23
Rope	69
Rope	10
Rope	13
Rope	24

Rope	10
Rope	64
Rope	45
Rope	73
Rope	30
Rope	22
Rope	29
Rope	28
Rope	16
Rope	34
Rope	73
Rope	67

We found a total of 34 concrete mooring blocks, 10 floating buoys, 9 possible floating buoys, 25 ropes of various length for a total length of about 1500 m. The floating buoys, instead, are generally made of high-density polyethylene (HDPE). Ropes for aquacultures are generally made mainly of polypropylene (PP). Given that generally a rope of about 20 mm of diameter has a linear weight of about 18 kg/100m (nylon ropes are even heavier), the estimated length of the ropes detected in the area could then be equivalent to about 270 kg of plastic material. The explored area corresponds to 2% of the whole mussel farm. Assuming a similar distribution of nets on the seafloor in the rest of the mussel farm would then imply that about 13.5 tons of plastic ropes could be lying on the seafloor.

At Sacca Fisola, a different method was applied to analyze the bathymetric data. The bathymetry data were analysed according to the ArcGIS workflow developed during the EASME/EMFF/2017/1.2.1.12/S2/05/SI2.789314 co-funded "marGnet" project (www.margnet.eu) and reported in the "marGnet" *Deliverable 3.2.1 Report on the experimental results*. The ArcGIS workflow was developed with the aim to extract semi-automatically ML targets from the bathymetry. The workflow modified the Pockmark Characterization Script described in Gafeira et al. (2012), and it is shown in Figure 24. So far, the workflow allowed discriminating between three different kinds of objects: tyres, poles (at least objects with shape that can be considered similar to tyres and poles) and others, a more generic category.

The data analysis process consists of six different steps and uses different ArcGIS tools run recursively.

- 1) The input is a bathymetric surface generated with Caris Hips & Sips after cleaning the raw MBES data. This step checks if Z values are positive before

starting the workflow, i.e. values increase with depth. If not, it calculates their negative values.

- 2) The Focal Statistics toolbox operates and generates a smoothed surface. In this way, it is possible to remove some background noise. Elaborating bad data with artifacts may lead the procedure to identify false objects.
- 3) The fill toolbox identifies confined depressions and fills them.
- 4) The “filled” bathymetry is subtracted from the original one by using the Minus toolbox. So, it can highlight the confined depressions.
- 5) Bathymetry is then classified in two classes, splitting all values with respect to a threshold of .02 m with the Reclassify tool. Then polygons were created with the Raster to Polygons tool. The class with values less than the threshold wasn't taken in account. Furthermore, a filter is applied on the polygon's areas rejecting polygons less than a threshold.
- 6) With the Minimum Boundary Tool new rectangular polygons were created, enveloping original polygons. After calculating the length of the sides of each polygon the length/width ratio was used to differentiate them. Polygons with ratio greater than 5 are defined “poles”, with ratio less than 1.4 are defined “tyres”.

Figure 24 - ArcGIS workflow to process bathymetric data.

Applying this workflow to the Sacca Fisola bathymetry allowed to identify a large number of possible targets, which are shown in Figure 25 and listed in Table 9.

Figure 25 - Map of detected objects in Sacca Fisola.

Table 9 - List of objects detected in Sacca Fisola

Object type	Number of items
Tyres	177
Poles	18
Others	264

The total number of identified objects is supposed to be overestimated. This may be due to the presence of noise and of irregularities in the bathymetric data that the tool interprets as possible targets.

Nevertheless, it provides a first estimation of the density of ML in very impacted areas (here estimated above 0.01 item/m²), useful to understand where to perform further investigation, such as video inspection with dedicated ROV.

5.3.1.2 Video inspection

Ten mini-ROV dives in the mussel farm area were conducted to validate the objects that were observed from MBES data (Figure 26). Based on the underwater videos, we observed

ropes/cables, buoys, metal cage, and “sassi” or a metal net with cobbles inside in the “Experimental field” area (Table 10). The ropes were sometimes installed in two layers i.e., one suspended on the water column and the other one is attached to the seabed. Buoys were heavily colonized by benthic species and were connected by ropes to the mooring blocks. The seabed appears to be very compact and composed of fine sediment.

Figure 26 - Location of the mini-ROV dives in the Coastal site in proximity of the Experimental Field and the designated buffer zone of 10 meters.

Table 10 - Examples of underwater images collected by the mini-ROV during the dives in the abandoned mussel farm in correspondence of the targets identified from the multibeam bathymetry (first column to the left) or backscatter intensity map (second column to the left). Identified objects were ropes/cables, metal cage and buoys.

<p>Dive 2</p> <p>X:12.595641 Y:45.450835</p>		cables or ropes connected to mooring block, rope of buoy			
<p>Dive 4</p> <p>X:12.592473 Y:45.450504</p>		ropes			
<p>Dive 5</p> <p>X:12.592653 Y:45.451279</p>		metal cage, metal net ("sassi") with cobbles inside			
<p>Dive 7</p> <p>X:12.594119 Y:45.452078</p>		cable or ropes attached to mooring block			
<p>Dive 8</p> <p>X:12.592915 Y:45.452627</p>		ropes, buoy			

The location of the five target areas for video survey performed at Sacca Fisola is presented in Figure 27. The survey in Sacca Fisola was a bit challenging because of poor water visibility and heavy traffic. According to the underwater videos, the seafloor is covered mostly by piles of concrete or construction debris, poles, metal bars, and household items such as plates, bottles, and bowls (Table 11). The tires that were observed in the MBES data were not visible in the mini-ROV camera because they might be buried by other objects. We also observed big objects (~1-2m) such as table, window, toilet bowl, wooden plank etc.

Figure 27 - Tracks followed during the video inspection (a) and the area buffers of each video (b).

Table 11 - Examples of underwater images that were collected during the surveys in the target areas in Sacca Fisola.

	MBES Image	Backscatter Image	ROV Images	
Dive 1 X:12.308124 Y:45.425993		tent, pipes, concrete debris		
Dive 2-3 X:12.308697 Y:45.425825		concrete debris		
Dive 4 X:12.309077 Y:45.425691		table, pots/vase, metal bar, concrete debris		
Dive 5 X:12.309077 Y:45.425572		bottles, bowl, plank of woods, concrete debris, metal bars		

5.3.2 Assessment of the biological community

5.3.2.1 Marine site: soft bottom macrozoobenthos

A total number of 1159 individuals belonging to 96 taxa have been identified. Of these, 14 taxa have been identified at the genus level, 1 at the subfamily level and 6 at the family level. Annelida, Arthropoda, Echinodermata, Mollusca and Sipunculida phyla are represented (the latter has recently been proposed to belong to the Annelida on the basis of molecular studies). A species, *Abyssoninoe hibernica* (McIntosh 1903), is not present in the Checklist of the Italian marine fauna (SIBM, 2008).

Selected univariate descriptors and indices are presented in Table 12. The aim is not to assess environmental quality, but rather to characterize the structure of the macrozoobenthic communities in the study sites. As previously stated, most of the indices, with the notable exception of density and AMBI, are dependent upon sample size. Difference in species richness between mean of replicates and whole-stations values indicates that species-area curves are far from reaching a plateau, and that the univariate index at the whole-station scale should be considered to give more robust information. However, observing the variability of the indexes between stations calculated at the replicate scale (boxplot in Figure 28), they seem not to drift too much apart (in particular in term of density and richness/diversity indexes). Since the same sampling protocol (and reference values for M-AMBI) was applied on both lagoon and marine site, it could be possible in the next phases of the project to compare directly the order of magnitude of change across sites.

Replicates	N	N m ⁻²	S	d	H'	J'	BC	M-AMBI
CS1A	147	1470	38	7.41	4.08	0.780	2.03	0.860
CS1B	224	2240	49	8.87	4.43	0.790	2.19	0.950
CS1C	203	2030	39	7.15	4.05	0.770	1.78	0.880
CS2A	159	1590	38	7.30	4.19	0.800	1.44	0.910
CS2B	213	2130	44	8.02	4.22	0.770	1.68	0.930
CS2C	213	2130	35	6.34	4.26	0.830	1.75	0.870
Mean of replicates								
CS1	191.3	1913.3	42	7.81	4.19	0.777	2.00	0.893
CS2	195.0	1950.0	39	7.22	4.22	0.800	1.63	0.902
Whole stations								

CS1	574	1913.3	74	11.49	4.48	0.72	2.00	0.97
CS2	585	1950.0	68	10.52	4.53	0.74	1.63	0.97

Table 12 – Univariate descriptors and indices calculated on soft bottom macrozoobenthos collected in the lagoon site.

Figure 28 – Boxplot of univariate descriptors and indices calculated on replicates, soft bottom macrozoobenthos collected in the marine site (the whiskers and the median correspond to the three points, whereas the boxes should be regarded as a visual hint at the skewness); the mean value of three replicates is shown with a red point.

Multivariate structures also show poor separation between stations, since replicates of each station did not form clear clusters nor separate clearly apart in NMDS ordination (Figure 29). This is also suggested by ANOSIM ($R = -0.148$; significance = 0.9) and ADONIS2 ($R^2 = 0.212$, $\rho = 0.4$), which however are not statistically significant. Overall, this may suggest rather homogenous macrozoobenthic communities over the marine site. Main taxonomic groups in terms of abundances for each replicate are presented in Figure 30, which may also give some insight in terms of trophic structure. The absolute as well as the proportional distribution of abundances are fairly comparable between replicates and between stations as well, with the predominance of polychaetes (both Errantia and Sedentaria) followed by amphipods and

echinoderms and, at a certain distance, bivalves. Other groups are characterized by smaller abundances.

Figure 29 – Cluster analysis (left; average group linkage on Bray-Curtis similarity) and NMDS (right; stress = 0.0694, circles proportional to species richness) performed on replicates, soft bottom macrozoobenthos collected in the marine site.

Figure 30 – Main taxonomic groups in terms of abundances, soft bottom macrozoobenthos collected in the marine site (AC: animalia cetera).

5.3.2.2 Marine site: hard substrate macrozoobenthos

At the present stage of the analysis, all the photomosaics on the selected faces were reconstructed (see Annex 2), and taxonomic identification based on available diagnostic features was performed. Due to high turbidity on 22/03/2022, part or all of the photographs composing photoquadrats 1A, 1B and 1C from the south pyramids have poor quality, therefore determining a low quality also in the taxonomic analysis and likely the underestimation of the species number.

The analysis of the photoquadrats allowed to identify 34 taxa, 18 of which were identified at the level of species or genus. Most of the observed species are sessile, belonging to 7 phyla: Annelida, Arthropoda, Bryozoa, Chordata Tunicata, Cnidaria, Mollusca Bivalvia and Porifera. Conversely, five species are vagile and belong to Echinodermata, Mollusca Gastropoda.

A first qualitative list of taxa identified for all photoquadrats is presented in Table 13. A preliminary semiquantitative matrix is presented in

Table 14, where for each replicate, species were separated into “dominant” and “companion”. All the frames of photoquadrat S1C are characterized by very poor quality, therefore this photoquadrat was excluded. In the north pyramid, vertical photoquadrats are characterized by a mean of 15 taxa, while the horizontal one has a mean of 10.7 taxa. In the south pyramid, the vertical photoquadrats have a mean of 12.5 and 12.7 taxa, while the horizontal one just 10 taxa.

The applied non-destructive technique has proved to be effective: the photoquadrates can reach very high quality and resolution, allowing to perform good taxonomical determination. Moreover, contrary to destructive samplings, it allows to study the biodiversity not disturbing organisms, guaranteeing at the same time the monitoring of the same points over time

Main issues include conditions of high turbidity and suspended sediments that can prevent the acquisition of images of adequate quality, and the limitations of the taxonomic determination through image analysis alone (which, by the way, describes only the external features). Therefore, unfortunately, this approach does not allow an adequate taxonomic resolution in relation to some groups, in particular to Porifera, which in the sampled stations have a primary role in terms of coverage and diversity.

Table 13 – Overall list of taxa identified in photoquadrats.

Phylum	Classis	Ordo	Familia	Taxon	Author
Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Serpulidae	cf. Spirobranchus triqueter	(Linnaeus, 1758)
Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Serpulidae	Serpulidae spp.	Rafinesque, 1815
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda		Amphipoda aff. Jassa	Leach, 1814
Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Schizoporellidae	cf. Schizoporella	Hincks, 1877
Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Schizoporellidae	Schizobrachiella sanguinea	(Norman, 1868)
Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida		Cheilostomatida indet.	
Chordata	Ascidiacea	Aplousobranchia	Didemnidae	Didemnidae sp.	Giard, 1872
Chordata	Ascidiacea	Stolidobranchia	Pyuridae	Microcosmus sp.	Heller, 1877
Cnidaria	Anthozoa	Scleractinia	Cladocoridae	cf. Cladocora caespitosa	(Linnaeus, 1767)
Cnidaria	Anthozoa	Zoantharia	Epizoanthidae	Epizoanthus sp.	Gray, 1867
Cnidaria	Hydrozoa			Hydrozoa	
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Gastrochaenida	Gastrochaenidae	Rocellaria dubia	(Pennant, 1777)
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Mytilida	Mytilidae	Mytilidae indet.	Rafinesque, 1815
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Ostreida	Ostreidae	Ostreidae indet.	Rafinesque, 1815
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Pectinida	Pectinidae	Pectinidae indet.	Rafinesque, 1815
Porifera	Demospongiae	Clionaida	Clionaidae	Cliona sp.	Grant, 1826
Porifera	Demospongiae	Dictyoceratida	Dysideidae	Dysidea avara	(Schmidt, 1862)
Porifera	Demospongiae	Dictyoceratida	Dysideidae	Dysidea fragilis	(Montagu, 1814)
Porifera	Demospongiae	Haplosclerida	Chalinidae	Haliclona sp.	Grant, 1841
Porifera	Demospongiae	Poecilosclerida	Microcionidae	Antho inconstans	(Topsent, 1925)
Porifera	Demospongiae	Poecilosclerida	Tedaniidae	Tedania anhelans	(Vio in Olivi, 1792)
Porifera	Demospongiae	Suberitida	Suberitidae	cf. Terpios	Duchassaing & Michelotti, 1864

Porifera	Demospongiae		Demospongiae indet. 1		
Porifera	Demospongiae		Demospongiae indet. 2		
Porifera	Demospongiae		Demospongiae indet. 3		
Porifera	Demospongiae		Demospongiae indet. 4		
Porifera	Demospongiae		Demospongiae indet. 5		
Porifera	Demospongiae		Demospongiae indet. 6		
Porifera	Demospongiae		Demospongiae indet. 7		
VAGILE SPECIES					
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda		Brachyura indet.	
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda		Decapoda indet. 2	
Echinodermata	Ophiuroidea	Amphilepidida	Amphiuridae	cf. Amphipholis (Delle Chiaje squamata 1828)	
Echinodermata	Ophiuroidea	Amphilepidida	Ophiotrichidae	Ophiothrix fragilis	(Abildgaard in O.F. Müller, 1789)
Mollusca	Gastropoda	Nudibranchia	Facelinidae	Cratena peregrina	(Gmelin, 1791)

Table 14 – Semiquantitative community matrix (XX: “dominant species”; X: “companion species”) and number of taxa per replicate; *: at least one out of 4 frames with high-quality; **: no frame with high-quality.

TAXON	N1A	N1B	N1C	N2A	N2B	N2C	N3A	N3B	N3C	S1A*	S1B*	S1C**	S2A	S2B	S2C	S3A	S3B	S3C
cf. Spirobranchus triqueter											X							
Serpulidae spp.	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X	X
Amphipoda aff. Jassa	X	XX	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			X	X			
cf. Schizoporella		X													X			
Schizobrachiella sanguinea	X	XX	X	XX	X	X	X	XX	X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Cheilostomatida indet.					X								X					
Didemnidae sp.				X	X					X	X							
Microcosmus sp.				X		X												
cf. Cladocora caespitosa															X			
Epizoanthus sp.	XX	XX	X	XX	XX	X	XX	XX	XX									

Hydrozoa	XX	XX	X	XX		XX	XX	XX	X	X								
Rocellaria dubia	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X			XX	XX	X
Mytilidae indet.																		X
Ostreidae indet.							X	X	X	X							X	
Pectinidae indet.	X														X			
Cliona sp.		X		X														X
Dysidea avara	XX	X	X	X		X							XX	XX	X			
Dysidea fragilis	XX	X		X	X								XX	X	X			
Haliclona sp.									X		X	X		X		X	X	X
Antho inconstans																		X
Tedania anhelans		X	X	X						X								
cf. Terpios	X	X			X	X							X		X			
Demospongiae indet. 1	XX		XX	XX	XX	XX	XX	XX										
Demospongiae indet. 2	XX			XX	XX		XX	XX	XX									
Demospongiae indet. 3	X										X							X
Demospongiae indet. 4			X		X													
Demospongiae indet. 5			X	X			X											
Demospongiae indet. 6				X														
Demospongiae indet. 7													X					
VAGILE SPECIES																		
Brachyura indet.							X											
Decapoda indet. 2	X																	
cf. Amphipholis squamata			X		X	X					X		X			X	X	
Ophiothrix fragilis	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X		X	X	X	X
Cratena peregrina		X							X									
number of taxa	15	16	14	17	15	13	12	9	11	11	14	3	14	10	14	9	10	11

A small colony (about 5X3 cm cover) of the pillow coral *Cladocora caespitosa* (Linnaeus, 1767) (Cnidaria: Scleractinia) was probably present in the south pyramid, photoquadrat S2C. However, due to the suboptimal quality of the image, the identification is uncertain and a "cf." qualifier has been chosen. *Cladocora caespitosa* is included in Annex II of the SPA/BD Protocol of the Barcelona Convention, and it is listed in the IUCN red list (2014), with "Least Concern" conservation status.

5.3.2.3 Lagoon site: soft bottom macrozoobenthos

A total number of 934 individuals belonging to 63 taxa was identified. Of these, 5 taxa have been identified at the genus level, 7 at the family level and 1 at the order level.

Annelida, Arthropoda, Echinodermata and Mollusca phyla are represented. Selected univariate descriptors and indices are presented in Table 15 and Figure 31. As already noticed before, also for these data it is possible to observe that most of the indices, with the notable exception of density and AMBI, are dependent upon sample size. The difference in species richness between mean of replicates and whole-station values indicates that species-area curves are far from reaching a plateau. Consequently, the univariate index at the whole-station scale should be considered to give more robust information. Compared to the marine site, the variability of the indexes between stations calculated at the replicate scale is generally higher, in particular in terms of density, evenness and AMBI-BC, whereas richness components of diversity stabilize on lower values (as per classical models of lagoon ecology); M-AMBI assumes similar values between stations as it averages different metrics.

Table 15 – Univariate descriptors and indices calculated on soft bottom macrozoobenthos dataset collected in the lagoon site.

Replicates	N	N m ⁻²	S	d	H'	J'	BC	M-AMBI
LV1A	150	1500	21	3.99	2.59	0.588	2.43	0.595
LV1B	239	2390	28	4.93	2.39	0.498	2.69	0.612
LV1C	149	1490	17	3.20	2.31	0.565	2.53	0.540
LV3A	113	1130	28	5.71	3.80	0.790	3.18	0.680
LV3B	164	1640	24	4.51	3.13	0.683	3.44	0.585
LV3C	119	1190	18	3.56	2.90	0.696	3.01	0.556
mean of replicates								
LV1	179.3	1793.3	22	4.04	2.43	0.550	2.55	0.582
LV2	132.0	1320.0	23.33	4.59	3.28	0.723	3.21	0.607
whole stations								
LV1	538	1793.3	40	6.20	2.59	0.487	2.55	0.719
LV3	396	1320.0	40	6.52	3.50	0.658	3.21	0.738

Figure 31– Boxplot of univariate descriptors and indices calculated on replicates, soft bottom macrozoobenthos collected in the lagoon site (the whiskers and the median corresponds to the three points, whereas the boxes should be regarded just as a visual hint at the skewness); the mean value of three replicates is shown with a red point.

Multivariate structures also show a better separation between stations, as showed both by clusters analysis and NMDS ordination (Figure 32). This is also suggested by ANOSIM ($R = 1$; significance = 0.1 and ADONIS2 ($R^2 = 0.807$, $\rho = 0.1$), which nevertheless once again show p -values above 0.05. This is somehow expected from both the MBES backscatter data available for the study area and direct observation of the texture of sampled sediments at the two stations. This may represent a disturbing factor in the comparison between impact and control. Main taxonomic groups in terms of abundances for each replicate are presented in Figure 33, which may also give some insight in terms of trophic structure. Sedentaria polychaets are by far the most represented group, followed by amphipods, bivalves, isopods and Errantia polychaetes (sample LV3C being characterized by a higher proportion of amphipods) with minor roughly comparable abundances. However, as showed by AMBI-BC index and therefore by the relative proportion of tollerant/sensitive species, taxonomic composition changes considerably across stations.

Figure 32 – Cluster analysis (left; average group linkage on Bray-Curtis similarity) and NMDS (right; stress = 0.0124, circles proportional to species richness) performed on replicates, soft bottom macrozoobenthos collected in the lagoon site.

Figure 33 – Main taxonomic groups in terms of abundances, soft bottom macrozoobenthos collected in the lagoon site (AC: animalia cetera).

5.3.2.4 Fish fauna

In the coastal site 7 specimens (total biomass 1,702 Kg) belonging to four different fish species were collected after one fishing day (Table 16). Some specimens, two spiny dogfish (*Squalus acanthias*) and one horse mackerel (*Trachurus trachurus*), were

found partially or almost totally in carcass form due to the presence of saprophagous isopods.

Table 16 – Coastal Site: abundance and biomass data of the specimens collected in each stations.

Species	Sampling stations	Abundance N°	Weight g
<i>Merlangius merlangus</i>	S1	1	98
<i>Squalus acanthias</i>	S1	1	1042*
<i>Merlangius merlangus</i>	S2	1	80
<i>Squalus acanthias</i>	S2	1	1372
<i>Squalus acanthias</i>	S3	1	834*
<i>Solea solea</i>	S4	1	152
<i>Trachurus trachurus</i>	S4	1	24*

* Weights should be considered as indicative as they refer to parasitized specimens.

In the lagoon site 733 specimens (biomass 22,789 Kg) belonging to 13 different fish species were sampled after three fishing days. Data related to the abundance and the biomass of each species collected within each of the 10 fike nets are reported in Table 17.

Table 17 – Lagoon site: abundance and biomass data of specimens collected in each fike net.

Species	Fike net	Abundance N°	Total Weight g
<i>Chelon auratus</i>	1	7	210
<i>Atherina boyeri</i>	1	85	230
<i>Zosterisessor ophiocephalus</i>	1	55	2900
<i>Atherina boyeri</i>	2	25	68
<i>Hippocampus guttulatus</i>	2	1	8
<i>Knipowitschia panizzae</i>	2	1	0,5
<i>Zosterisessor ophiocephalus</i>	2	38	2000
<i>Chelon auratus</i>	3	9	270
<i>Chelon ramada</i>	3	1	19
<i>Solea solea</i>	3	1	17
<i>Atherina boyeri</i>	3	40	108
<i>Knipowitschia panizzae</i>	3	1	0,5
<i>Gobius niger</i>	3	1	14

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<i>Pomatoschistus marmoratus</i>	3	1	1
<i>Hippocampus guttulatus</i>	3	1	8
<i>Zosterisessor ophiocephalus</i>	3	38	2000
<i>Atherina boyeri</i>	4	20	54
<i>Zosterisessor ophiocephalus</i>	4	47	2480
<i>Chelon auratus</i>	5	2	60
<i>Atherina boyeri</i>	5	10	27
<i>Pomatoschistus marmoratus</i>	5	1	1
<i>Zosterisessor ophiocephalus</i>	5	28	1480
<i>Atherina boyeri</i>	6	30	81
<i>Zosterisessor ophiocephalus</i>	6	38	2000
<i>Chelon auratus</i>	7	3	90
<i>Solea solea</i>	7	1	16
<i>Pomatoschistus marmoratus</i>	7	3	2,9
<i>Atherina boyeri</i>	7	25	67,5
<i>Zosterisessor ophiocephalus</i>	7	45	2360
<i>Chelon auratus</i>	8	4	120
<i>Chelon ramada</i>	8	1	19
<i>Atherina boyeri</i>	8	30	81
<i>Zosterisessor ophiocephalus</i>	8	15	800
<i>Chelon auratus</i>	9	1	30
<i>Chelon labrosus</i>	9	1	28
<i>Symphodus roissali</i>	9	1	38
<i>Gobius paganellus</i>	9	1	14
<i>Solea solea</i>	9	1	15
<i>Zosterisessor ophiocephalus</i>	9	25	1320
<i>Solea solea</i>	10	1	16
<i>Chelon auratus</i>	10	2	60
<i>Chelon ramada</i>	10	4	92
<i>Syngnathus typhle</i>	10	1	15
<i>Atherina boyeri</i>	10	20	54
<i>Gobius paganellus</i>	10	1	14

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<i>Zosterisessor ophiocephalus</i>	10	66	3500
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The most abundant species (both in terms of abundance and biomass) were the grass goby (*Zosterisessor ophiocephalus*), the big-scale sand smelt (*Atherina boyeri*), the golden grey mullet (*Chelon auratus*), and the thinlip mullet (*Chelon ramada*) (Table 18).

The CPUE abundance values ranged from 13.17 ± 4.94 specimens for *Z. ophiocephalus* to 0.03 ± 0.11 specimens for *G. niger*, *S. roissali*, *C. labrosus* and *S. typhle*. Similarly, the CPUE biomass values ranged from 694.67 ± 261.1 gr for *Z. ophiocephalus* to 0.03 ± 0.07 gr for *K. panizzae*.

Table 18 – Catch per unit effort (CPUE) values for abundance (n°) and biomass (gr) [Mean (St. Dev)] of each fish species collected in the lagoon site.

Family	Species	CPUE N°	CPUE g
Atherinidae	<i>Atherina boyeri</i>	9.5 (7.58)	25.68 (20.51)
Gobiidae	<i>Gobius niger</i>	0.03 (0.11)	0.47 (1.48)
	<i>Gobius paganellus</i>	0.07 (0.14)	0.93 (1.97)
	<i>Knipowitschia panizzae</i>	0.07 (0.14)	0.03 (0.07)
	<i>Pomatoschistus marmoratus</i>	0.17 (0.32)	0.16 (0.31)
	<i>Zosterisessor ophiocephalus</i>	13.17 (4.94)	694.67 (261.1)
Labridae	<i>Symphodus roissali</i>	0.03 (0.11)	1.27 (4.01)
Mugilidae	<i>Chelon auratus</i>	0.93 (1.03)	28 (30.84)
	<i>Chelon labrosus</i>	0.03 (0.11)	0.93 (2.95)
	<i>Chelon ramada</i>	0.2 (0.42)	4.33 (9.62)
Soleidae	<i>Solea solea</i>	0.13 (0.17)	2.13 (2.76)
Syngnathidae	<i>Hippocampus guttulatus</i>	0.07 (0.14)	0.53 (1.12)
	<i>Syngnathus typhle</i>	0.03 (0.11)	0.5 (1.58)

The diversity indexes determined for fish community collected in coastal and lagoon sites are shown in Table 19.

In general, indices calculated for the coastal site are not relevant as they are influenced by the low number of sampled organisms. Conversely, the lagoon site is characterized by the presence of a fish community with high number of taxa. However, as 92% of all captured fish belong to only two species (*A. boyeri* and *Z. ophiocephalus*) the Shannon and Margalef indexes calculated for the lagoon site evidenced the presence of low levels of complexity in the structure of lagoon fish community.

Table 19 – Diversity indexes of fish community calculated for lagoon and coastal site

Diversity index	Sacca Fisola (Lagoon site)	Mussel farm (Coastal site)
<i>Taxa (S)</i>	13	4
<i>Richness (total number of organisms)</i>	733	7
<i>Margalef (D)</i>	1.82	1.54
<i>Shannon (H')</i>	0,995	1,25

5.3.3 Microplastic assesment

5.3.3.1 Microplastics assessment in surface waters

The main field parameters detected during each survey and data on microplastic particles are reported in Table 20 and Table 21, respectively. In the three transects (1-3), the concentration of microplastics observed at Sacca Fisola, the Lagoon site, ranged from 1.65 to 4.34 particles m^{-3} , whereas at the mussel farm located in the marine coastal area the concentrations ranged from 0.95 to 1.12 particles m^{-3} . The total amount of microplastics collected along the three transects at the coastal site were generally lower and distributed more homogeneously among transects than at Sacca Fisola. The mean values of the n. particles m^{-3} calculated with the values detected in the three transects were 2.98 ± 0.78 (S.E.) at Sacca Fisola and 1.05 ± 0.05 (S.E.) at the coastal area. The Mann-Whitney test highlighted a significant difference between the two mean values for $p < 0.05$ (Figure 34).

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The quantity of microplastics, classified according to their colour and shape, showed a similar % in the three transects in each sampling site, although differences were observed when comparing the two stations. White microplastic particles were the most abundant at Sacca Fisola, accounting for about 60%, whereas blue particles were the most abundant at the mussel farm (Figure 35). Irregular fragments, filaments and spheres were the most abundant shapes observed at Sacca Fisola. Conversely, filaments was the most abundant shape observed at the mussel farm (Figure 36).

The tables 1 and 2 reporting all the raw data for each transect of the two stations are enclosed as Annex 3.

Some preliminary considerations can be drawn, although they will require more in-depth analyses. The white spheres found at Sacca Fisola are probably made of polystyrene, derived from food service utensils or boxes used for the conservation of commercial fish and seafood, or primary plastic material used for the industrial production of Expanded Polystyrene Foam (Vianello et al., 2018). Conversely, the blue filaments, abundantly found at the mussel farm, could derive from the ropes and nets used to harvest mussels.

Table 20 – Stations and environmental parameters recorded during the surveys at Sacca Fisola (Lagoon site) and at the mussel farm (Marine coastal site). For each station are given: sampling date, geographic coordinates of start and end of sampling, average boat speed (kn), sea state (Douglas scale), wind force (Beaufort scale), wind direction, sea surface temperature (°C) and salinity (psu).

Station	Transect	Sampling date	Starting coord. (Lat)	Starting coord. (Long)	Ending coord. (Lat)	Ending coord. (Long)	Trawling Speed	Sea state	Wind force	Wind direction	Temp.	Salinity
Sacca Fisola	1	23/02/2022	45° 25.560	12° 18.386	45° 25.533	12° 19.016	1.8	0	1	S-SW	8.6	n.d.
	2	23/02/2022	-	-	-	-	1.8	0	1	S-SW	8.6	n.d.
	3	23/02/2022	-	-	-	-	1.8	0	1	S-SW	8.7	n.d.
Mussel farm	1	21/02/2022	45° 27.153	12° 35.686	45° 26.613	12° 35.747	1.8	2	1	N-E	8.5	36.1
	2	21/02/2022	45° 27.419	12° 35.635	45° 26.648	12° 35.744	1.8	2	1	N-E	8.5	36.0
	3	21/02/2022	45° 27.305	12° 35.660	45° 26.904	12° 34.923	1.8	2	1	N-E	8.5	36.0

Table 21 - Total water volume filtered by the Manta, total number of microplastics and number of microplastics/m³ collected during the sampling surveys at Sacca Fisola (Lagoon site) and at the mussel farm (Marine coastal site).

Transect	Station	Filtered volume (m ³)	N. particles	N. particles m ⁻³
Sacca Fisola	1	70.3	305	4.34
	2	63.6	188	2.96
	2	77.7	128	1.65
Mussel farm	1	92.4	88	0.95
	2	97.2	104	1.07
	3	114.8	129	1.12

Figure 34 – Mean number of particles per m³ in the samples collected at Sacca Fisola (Lagoon site) and at the mussel farm (Marine coastal site). Mean \pm s.e., N = 3. Mann-Whitney test * ρ < 0.05.

Figure 35 – Classification of microplastic particles (in %) according to colour. Samples collected at Sacca Fisola (Lagoon site) and at the mussel farm (Marine coastal site).

Figure 36 – Classification of microplastic particles (in %) according to shape. Samples collected at Sacca Fisola (Lagoon site) and at the mussel farm (Marine coastal site).

5.3.3.2 Microplastic assesment in sediments

The data on microplastic particles are reported in Table 22. The concentration of microplastics observed in the sediments collected in both sites showed a high variability among replicates. At Sacca Fisola, the Lagoon site, the microplastic concentrations ranged in the five replicates from 156 to 407 particles kg^{-1} , whereas at the mussel farm located in the marine coastal area the concentrations ranged from 184 to 522 particles kg^{-1} . The mean values of the particles kg^{-1} calculated with the values detected in the five replicates are 304.3 ± 44.0 (S.E.) at Sacca Fisola and 327.8

± 55.6 (S.E.) at the mussel farm. The Mann–Whitney test highlighted no significant difference between the two mean values ($p > 0.05$) (Figure 37).

The quantity of microplastics, classified according to their colour and shape, showed a similar % in both comparing the replicates within each site and between the two sampled areas (Figure 38 and Figure 39). Blue and transparent microplastic particles were the most abundant, accounting for 40% in almost all samples. Filaments were the most abundant shapes observed in all samples, accounting for 50 % or more in all the analyzed samples.

The tables 3 and 4 reporting all the raw data for each transect of the two stations are enclosed in the Annex 3.

Table 22 - Wet weight of sediment (in gr), total number of microplastics and number of microplastics/kg (WW) collected during the sampling surveys at Sacca Fisola (Lagoon site) and at the mussel farm (Marine coastal site).

Sampling Site	Grab Replicate	WW (gr)	N. particles	N. particles Kg ⁻¹
Sacca Fisola	1	250.5	102	407
	2	250.3	65	260
	3	250.2	87	348
	4	250.1	39	156
	5	250.7	88	351
Mussel farm	1	248.4	87	350
	2	250.8	131	522
	3	247.2	71	287
	4	250.7	74	295
	5	250.4	46	184

Figure 37 – Mean number of particles per kg (ww) in the samples collected at Sacca Fisola (Lagoon site) and at the mussel farm (Marine coastal site). Mean \pm s.e., N = 5. Mann-Whitney test n.s. $\rho > 0.05$.

Figure 38 – Classification of microplastic particles (in %) according to colour. Samples collected at Sacca Fisola (Lagoon site) and at the mussel farm (Marine coastal site).

Figure 39 – Classification of microplastic particles (in %) according to shape. Samples collected at Sacca Fisola (Lagoon site) and at the mussel farm (Marine coastal site).

For each sediment replicate, the sediment grain size was also determined (see Table 23). Sediments of the coastal site (i.e. mussel farm) were mainly composed by the sand fraction, with a mean value of 65 ± 10 . On the contrary, sediments from the lagoon site (i.e. Sacca Fisola) are mainly muddy, with a mean value of 79 ± 7 .

Table 23 – Grain size distribution (in %) of the sediment replicates collected in the two demo site of the Venice coastal area (Coastal site: the abandoned mussel farm; lagoon site: Sacca Fisola).

	Mussel farm					Sacca Fisola				
	Rep1	Rep2	Rep3	Rep4	Rep5	Rep1	Rep2	Rep3	Rep4	Rep5
GRAVEL	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
SAND	64.8	71.9	49.5	76.9	61.8	24.5	15.1	16.4	31.6	15.8
MUD	35.2	28.1	50.5	23.1	38.2	75.5	84.9	83.6	68.4	84.2

5.3.3.3 Microplastic assessment in biota

Preliminary data on microplastics determined in mussel tissues are reported in Table 24. The concentration of microplastics observed in the mussel soft tissues collected in the lagoon site (Sacca Fisola) showed a higher variability among individuals than the MP concentration determined in mussels from the coastal area (the abandoned mussel farm). At Sacca Fisola, microplastic concentrations ranged from 2.51 to 9.17 particles g^{-1} , whereas at the mussel farm the concentrations ranged from 1.95 to 2.53 particles g^{-1} . The mean values are 4.90 ± 2.14 (S.E.) particles g^{-1} at Sacca Fisola and 2.10 ± 0.13 (S.E.) particles g^{-1} at the mussel farm. The Mann-Whitney test highlighted no

significant difference between the samples from the two sampling sites ($p > 0.05$) (Figure 40).

The quantity of microplastics, classified according to their color and shape, showed some differences between the two samples (Figure 41 and Figure 42). Blue and red microplastic particles were the most abundant both in marine coastal and lagoon mussels accounting for 53%-94% of the total of particles. Filaments were the most abundant shapes in mussels from Sacca Fisola, whereas films were the most abundant shape of microplastics in mussel from the marine coastal area, accounting for at least 67% and 33%, respectively.

Table 24 – Length (L), wet weight (WW) of mussels, total number of microplastics and number of microplastics/gr (WW) collected during the sampling surveys at the mussel farm (Marine coastal site) and Sacca Fisola (Lagoon site).

Sampling Site	Individual	L (cm)	WW (g)	N. particles	N. particles g ⁻¹
Mussel farm	1	6.02	5.53	11	1.99
	2	6.90	9.22	18	1.95
	3	6.27	7.18	17	2.37
Sacca Fisola	1	6.21	5.63	17	3.02
	2	6.10	8.36	21	2.51
	3	6.26	6.11	56	9.17

Figure 40 – Mean number of particles per g (ww) in the samples collected at the mussel farm (Marine coastal site) and Sacca Fisola (Lagoon site). Mean \pm s.e., N = 3. Mann-Whitney test: $p > 0.05$.

Figure 41 – Classification of microplastic particles observed in mussels (in %) according to colour. Samples collected at Sacca Fisola (Lagoon site) and at the mussel farm (Marine coastal site).

Figure 42 – Classification of microplastic particles observed in mussels (in %) according to shape. Samples collected at the mussel farm (Marine coastal site) and at Sacca Fisola (Lagoon site).

5.3.4 Micro-contaminant evaluation in water

None of the analytes detailed in Table 25 was quantitated because their amounts were always below the Limit of Quantitation (LOQ) that corresponds to the lowest analyte concentration, which can reliably be numerically quantified.

From a careful observation of the chromatograms, some peaks corresponding to specific analytes are present. The Limit of Detection (LOD) is defined by IUPAC as “the

smallest concentration or absolute amount of analyte that has a signal significantly larger than the signal from a suitable blank". If this is the case, we may affirm that a specific analyte is present in the sample even if we cannot quantitate it because the background noise would impair the numerical estimate of its quantity. It is possible to observe that:

- in the coastal site sample, Ethylbenzene e o-m-p-Xylene (Aromatic Hydrocarbons, benzo(a)pyrene, anthracene, fluoranthene, and pyrene (PAHs) are present at concentrations above the LOD but below the LOQ;
- in the Lagoon site sample, benzo(a)pyrene, anthracene, fluoranthene and pyrene (PAHs) are present at concentrations above the LOD but below the LOQ and, however, higher than the corresponding analytes in the coastal site;

It is important to emphasise that the present analytical approach follows the standard National Research Council methods cited above, but the extremely low concentrations of organic pollutants may require a different analytical approach.

Noteworthy, the standard National Research Council methods are "targeted method", which means that only analytes included in an "a priori" list are searched by the analytical processing method which enables detection and, possibly, quantitation. It follows that many analytes which are not searched for will not be found.

In order to monitor different sites for a long period of time, the absolute amounts of analytes may not be needed since only a comparative evaluation is useful. In this case, the HS-SPME-GC-MS analytical strategy would be highly recommended. It was already used to test the presence of contaminants related to marine litter in Venice Lagoon before and after the COVID-19 Pandemic. Striking results can be found in Cecchi (2021). The quantitative use of this strategy is possible, but requires the commercial standard of the analytical grade of each detected compound.

Table 25 – Chemical analyses on water samples.

Compound		1 coastal site		2 lagoon site	Method
1,2,3- trimethylbenzene (mg/l)	<	0.0005	<	0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5140 Man 29 2003
1,2,4- trimethylbenzene (mg/l)	<	0.0005	<	0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5140 Man 29 2004
1,3,5- trimethylbenzene (mg/l)	<	0.0005	<	0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5140 Man 29 2005

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1,2- dimethylbenzene (mg/l)	< 0.0005	< 0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5140 Man 29 2006
1,4- dimethylbenzene (mg/l)	< 0.0005	< 0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5140 Man 29 2007
1-Ethyl-2,4- dimethylbenzene< (mg/l)	0.0005	< 0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5140 Man 29 2008
2-Ethyl-1,4- dimethylbenzene< (mg/l)	0.0005	< 0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5140 Man 29 2009
Benzene (mg/l)	< 0.0005	< 0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5140 Man 29 2010
Butylbenzene (mg/l)	< 0.0005	< 0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5140 Man 29 2011
Ethylbenzene (mg/l)	< 0.0005	< 0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5140 Man 29 2012
Cumene (mg/l)	< 0.0005	< 0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5140 Man 29 2013
Ethyltoluene (mg/l)	< 0.0005	< 0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5140 Man 29 2014
Indane (mg/l)	< 0.0005	< 0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5140 Man 29 2015
Propylbenzene (mg/l)	< 0.0005	< 0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5140 Man 29 2016
1-Methyl-2-Propylbenzene (mg/l)	< 0.0005	< 0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5140 Man 29 2017
1-Methyl-2-Propylbenzene (mg/l)	< 0.0005	< 0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5140 Man 29 2017
1-Ethyl-2-Methylbenzene (mg/l)	< 0.0005	< 0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5140 Man 29 2018
1-Ethyl-3-Methylbenzene (mg/l)	< 0.0005	< 0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5140 Man 29 2019
1-Ethyl-4-Methylbenzene (mg/l)	< 0.0005	< 0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5140 Man 29 2020
Styrene (mg/l)	< 0.0005	< 0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5140 Man 29 2021
Toluene (mg/l)	< 0.0005	< 0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5140 Man 29 2022
Xilenes (o+m+p) (mg/l)	< 0.0005	< 0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5140 Man 29 2023
1,1,1- trichloroethane (mg/l)	< 0.0005	< 0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5150 Man 29 2003
1,1,2,2-Tetrachloroethane (mg/l)	< 0.0005	< 0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5150 Man 29 2004
1,2-Dichloroetane (mg/l)	< 0.0005	< 0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5150 Man 29 2005
1,2-Dichloropropane (mg/l)	< 0.0005	< 0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5150 Man 29 2006
2,2,2- trichloroethanol (mg/l)<	0.0005	< 0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5150 Man 29 2007
Chlorobenzene (mg/l)	< 0.0005	< 0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5150 Man 29 2008
Chloroform (mg/l)	< 0.0005	< 0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5150 Man 29 2009
Chlorotoluene (mg/l)	< 0.0005	< 0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5150 Man 29 2010
Hexachloro-1,3-butadiene (mg/l)	< 0.0005	< 0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5150 Man 29 2011
Hexachlorobenzene (mg/l)	< 0.0005	< 0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5150 Man 29 2012
Hexachlorocloroetane (mg/l)	< 0.0005	< 0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5150 Man 29 2013

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Methylenecloruro (mg/l)	<	0.0005	<	0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5150 Man 29 2014
Tetrachloroethylene (mg/l)	<	0.0005	<	0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5150 Man 29 2015
carbon tetrachloride (mg/l)	<	0.0005	<	0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5150 Man 29 2016
Trichloroethylene (mg/l)	<	0.0005	<	0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5150 Man 29 2017
1,1,2,3-Tetrachloropropane (mg/l)	<	0.0005	<	0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5150 Man 29 2018
1,2,3-Trichloropropane (mg/l)	<	0.0005	<	0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5150 Man 29 2019
1,2,3-Trichloropropane (mg/l)	<	0.0005	<	0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5150 Man 29 2019
(o-m-p)-Dichlorobenzene (mg/l)	<	0.0005	<	0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5150 Man 29 2020
3,cloro-2,cloromethyl-1,propene (mg/l)	<	0.0005	<	0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5150 Man 29 2021
1,1,3,3-tetrachloro-2,methyl-propene (mg/l)	<	0.0005	<	0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5150 Man 29 2022
1,1,2-Tetrachloropropane (mg/l)	<	0.0005	<	0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5150 Man 29 2023
Benzo (a) pyrene (mg/l)	<	0.00001	<	0.00001	APAT CNR IRSA 5080 Man 29 2003
Dibenzo (a,h) anthracene (mg/l)	<	0.00001	<	0.00001	APAT CNR IRSA 5080 Man 29 2004
Benzo (e) fluorantene (mg/l)	<	0.00001	<	0.00001	APAT CNR IRSA 5080 Man 29 2005
Benzo (j) fluoranthene (mg/l)	<	0.00001	<	0.00001	APAT CNR IRSA 5080 Man 29 2006
Benzo (k) fluoranthene (mg/l)	<	0.00001	<	0.00001	APAT CNR IRSA 5080 Man 29 2007
Benzo (a) anthracene (mg/l)	<	0.00001	<	0.00001	APAT CNR IRSA 5080 Man 29 2008
Chrysene (mg/l)	<	0.00001	<	0.00001	APAT CNR IRSA 5080 Man 29 2009
Acenaphthene (mg/l)	<	0.00001	<	0.00001	APAT CNR IRSA 5080 Man 29 2010
Acenaphthene (µg/ml)	<	0.00001	<	0.00001	APAT CNR IRSA 5080 Man 29 2011
Acenaphtylene (mg/l)	<	0.00001	<	0.00001	APAT CNR IRSA 5080 Man 29 2012
Fluorene (mg/l)	<	0.00001	<	0.00001	APAT CNR IRSA 5080 Man 29 2013
Phenanthrene (mg/l)	<	0.00001	<	0.00001	APAT CNR IRSA 5080 Man 29 2014
Antracene (mg/l)	<	0.00001	<	0.00001	APAT CNR IRSA 5080 Man 29 2015
Antracene (µg/ml)	<	0.00001	<	0.00001	APAT CNR IRSA 5080 Man 29 2016
Fluoranthene (mg/l)	<	0.00001	<	0.00001	APAT CNR IRSA 5080 Man 29 2017
Pyrene (mg/l)	<	0.00001	<	0.00001	APAT CNR IRSA 5080 Man 29 2018
Benzo (g,h,i) perylene (mg/l)	<	0.00001	<	0.00001	APAT CNR IRSA 5080 Man 29 2019
Indeno (1,2,3-cd) pyrene (mg/l)	<	0.00001	<	0.00001	APAT CNR IRSA 5080 Man 29 2020
Dibenzo (a,e) pyrene (mg/l)	<	0.00001	<	0.00001	APAT CNR IRSA 5080 Man 29 2021
Dibenzo (a,h)pyrene (mg/l)	<	0.00001	<	0.00001	APAT CNR IRSA 5080 Man 29 2022
Dibenzo (a,i)pyrene (mg/l)	<	0.00001	<	0.00001	APAT CNR IRSA 5080 Man 29 2023

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Dibenzo (a,l)pyrene (mg/l)	<	0.00001	<	0.00001	APAT CNR IRSA 5080 Man 29 2024
Naphthalene (mg/l)	<	0.00001	<	0.00001	APAT CNR IRSA 5080 Man 29 2025
Aliphatic Hydrocarbons C5-<C8 (mg/l)		0.0005	<	0.0005	APAT CNR IRSA 5140 Man 29 2003
Hydrocarbons C10-C40 (mg/l)	<	0.15	<	0.15	UNI EN ISO 9377-2:2002

5.4 Conclusions

The results obtained in the pre-cleaning ecosystem assessment performed in the two sites of the Venice coast (the costal site, i.e. the abandoned mussel farm; the lagoon site, i.e. Sacca Fisola), highlighted the presence in both areas of accumulated ML. In particular, the coastal area is characterized by litter deriving from aquaculture activities, such as nets, buoys and ropes, whereas Sacca Fisola is characterized by items originating from urban activities (such as tyres, piles but also bowls and bottles). Microplastics were identified as well in superficial waters, sediments and mussels.

The assessment of the biological communities allowed to identify the main macrozoobenthos and fish species, as well as their abundances in both areas. Moreover, the presence of macrozoobenthic endangered/protected or valuable species, that due to their sessile and sedentary habit could be more affected by the seabed cleaning platform operations, was not identified on the areas directly interested by the cleaning activities. This result fulfills also the requirements of the Deliverable 10.3 - EPQ Requirement No. 3 on the ethical aspects related to the Environmental protection and safety.

6 Case study: Ave River estuary, Portugal

6.1 Ecological assessment in the Ave River estuary

Transitional ecosystems are among the most degraded areas on the planet and those most subjected to the effects of climate change and human pressures. Many human activities affect water quality, including agriculture, industry, urbanisation, disposal of human waste, pollution, mining, and climate change. In 2000, the European Union established its framework for the protection, improvement, and sustainable use of Europe's water resources by launching the Water Framework Directive (WFD, 2000). The WFD was pioneering because its approach integrates both the chemical

and ecological states in defining water quality (Vincent, 2002). Although the Directive requires the assessment of hydromorphological, physical and chemical elements, the assessment of the biological communities is necessary to assess the ecological status, through the analysis of the structure of macroinvertebrate, fish, macrophyte, phytobenthos and phytoplankton communities. The classification scheme (Figure 43) illustrates how the different analysed elements are combined and how the “one-out, all-out” principle is applied to achieve the final water quality classification.

The measurement of the ecological status makes it possible to evaluate the effect of human activity on water ecosystems, being an essential tool for the sustainable management of water resources. The legislation requires the periodic assessment of all water bodies, including rivers, lakes, estuaries, coastal waters and groundwaters. Moreover, the water body typology is essential to select the type-specific approach to the estimation of the water quality. Water types are then assigned to a classification system that grades their deviation from reference state (Figure 44; high, good, moderate, poor and bad), with no, or very minor, disturbance from human activities. The main objective of the WFD is to implement measures to achieve “good ecological status” of all natural water bodies.

Figure 43 – Water Framework Directive classification scheme of surface water status using “one-out, all-out” principle; H – high status, G – good status, M – moderate status, P – poor status, B – bad status.

Figure 44 – Ecological Quality Ratio (EQR) used to determine the ecological water quality status regarding the biological parameters.

Micro and macro litter represent another issue contributing to the degradation of water bodies, although these parameters are not evaluated in the WFD. However, their impact on the aquatic ecosystems, in particular on the biota and food webs, is not completely understood. Macro litter has become a dilemma for the whole society, affecting all sectors: economic, social, environmental and even cultural, thus increasingly becoming a multigenerational problem. Macro litter is mostly discharged into aquatic ecosystems and transported by currents to diverse areas, also far from their sources. Macrolitter is composed of a wide variety of materials from various sources; however, plastics are, by far, the most abundant material recorded (Arthur et al., 2009). Plastic marine debris are exposed to physical, chemical and biological stressors, resulting in smaller fragments, known as microplastics (Gago et al., 2018). The growing input of both macro litter and microplastics is causing a wide spectrum of environmental, economic and social impacts.

Rivers act as pipelines to the ocean, channelling the waste that is dumped into the estuaries. Thus, acquiring data on these ecosystems contribute to a better understanding on the accumulation of litter into the ocean from terrestrial sources. To increase the knowledge on the contamination impacts on wild populations by both anthropogenic macro litter and microplastic, more biomonitoring studies on those areas are still and urgently needed, also in order to support appropriate management measures. In addition, these field monitoring are being considered crucial in the scope of national and international regulations, such as the Marine Strategy Framework Directive of the European Union (Directive 2008/56/EC).

The Ave River hydrological basin has been monitored since 2009 for its ecological status/potential in compliance with the WFD (Water Framework Directive - 2nd River Basin Management Plans - <https://eea.maps.arcgis.com/home/item.html?id=b9599ba3963c4b8ca925e727573350>

36). This assessment has been made in three monitoring cycles, and the evaluation is represented in Figure 45. The ecological assessment revealed a degradation of the ecosystems at the last part of the Ave River, including its estuary, reaching the worst classification (Bad) in the last monitoring programme (2022-2027; Figure 4; PGRH, 2022). According to the monitoring programmes, the degradation of the ecological status of the Ave River estuary over time is associated to the increase of anthropogenic pressures, namely: augment of the population, urban environment, tourism, and recreational activities. Moreover, the increase of industrial activities in the entire hydrographic basin (Figure 2 and Table 1) is a factor that influence the quality of water ecosystem. Another factor is the decrease of freshwater fluxes due to climate change (augmenting the residence time of the water masses inside the estuary). This is a common pattern in Portuguese estuaries, however, there is not up-to-date data for Ave River estuary that can corroborate this reduction in the freshwater fluxes.

Figure 45 – Ave hydrographic basin with the final classification of the ecological status/potential for the three monitoring programmes according to the WFD metrics (source: <https://sniamb.apambiente.pt/>; APA, 2021).

6.2 Methodologies

Three sampling sites were selected to assess the ecological status of Ave estuary. In each site, water and sediments were collected to assess the ecological status of the transitional ecosystems regarding the European current legislation – WFD. The

sampling periods for the first evaluation (zero time) were carried out for spring and autumn seasons (spring 2021, autumn 2021, and spring 2022) before the implementation of the cleaning technology (Figure 46). The marine litter evaluation was also conducted in the same periods to characterize and quantify macro litter and microplastics along five transects, covering the same estuarine area (Figure 47 and Figure 48). Additional campaigns were performed in the same period to understand the hydrodynamic and morphological characteristics of this estuarine region, their links with the ecological status of the Ave River estuary and the macro litter and microplastics transport (Figure 49).

Figure 46— Sampling campaigns for the ecological status of Ave estuary.

Figure 47 – Sampling campaigns for the macro-litter and microplastics status of Ave estuary.

Figure 48 – Location of selected sampling transects (T1-T5) for microplastics collection in the downstream Ave River estuary.

Figure 49– Sampling campaigns for the hydrodynamic and morphological status of Ave estuary.

6.2.1 *In situ* methodologies

In each of the selected sites, using a boat, physical and chemical parameters were measured sub-superficially (<0.50 m depth) in water: pH, conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), salinity and dissolved oxygen (mg/L and %) were detected using a multiparameter probe (Multi 3630 IDS SET F). The photic water layer depth was also measured with the Secchi disk. Additionally, water samples were collected and transported to the laboratory at 4°C under dark conditions for further analyses (e.g. chlorophyll *a*, nutrients, metals, pesticides and biotoxins). For the phytoplankton community characterization, 500 mL of water samples were collected and immediately conserved in Lugol.

Macroinvertebrate community samples were collected using a Van Veen grab ($\approx 0.051 \text{ m}^2$ of area). In each site, three drags were performed and the sediment samples were preserved in formaldehyde 4% with Rose Bengal dye. One additional sediment sample was collected in each site for further analysis: organic matter content and granulometry.

Marine litter and microplastics were assessed during the same periods following international guidelines. The evaluation of macro litter was performed through visual monitoring (Gago et al., 2018; González-Fernández, 2018). Microplastic particles were

sampled using the same boat, by a horizontal trawl using a 200 μm planktonic net, equipped with a flowmeter (Frias et al., 2019; 2022). Samples were stored in glass bottles, transported to laboratory and cooled for further laboratory analysis.

Physical parameters were measured to understand the hydrodynamic behaviour of the Ave River estuary. Two boat campaigns with a duration of 13 h encompassing an entire spring tide cycle were performed in October 2021 and January 2022. The campaigns consisted in 13 hourly transects between CMIA (the north margin) and SICNAVE (the south margin), measuring vertical profiles of current velocity, salinity, temperature and pH with an ADCP and a multiparametric probe (Figure 50).

Figure 50 - Scheme of the hydrodynamic campaigns performed in the Ave River estuary.

6.2.2 Laboratory procedures

In the laboratory, nutrient quantification (Nitrites (NO_2^-), nitrates (NO_3^-), ammonia ($\text{NH}_3 + \text{NH}_4^+$) and phosphates (PO_4^{3-}) was obtained using a Skalar SAN+ Segmented Flow Analyzer using the following Skalar methods: M461-318 (EPA 353.2), M155-008R (EPA 350.1), and M503-555R (Standard Method 450-P I). For metals analysis (mercury (Hg), lead (Pb), copper (Cu), cadmium (Cd) and nickel (Ni)), the methods used were the Flame Atomic Absorption Spectrometry and the Electrothermal Atomic Absorption.

The determination of cyanotoxins was carried out by sonication of a water sample (≈ 400 mL) in ultrasound, with the objective of homogenization and cell lysis. Sample concentration/cleaning was performed on a dual solid phase cartridge system C-18 and activated carbon. The investigation of cyanotoxins (Anatoxin,

Cylindrospermopsin, Microcystins, and Saxitoxin) was performed by liquid chromatography technique coupled with a mass spectrometry detector in the Waters MicroMass® system. Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs) were determined in water samples in the analytical method Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS), while the per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAs) were determined in a LC-MS.

Water samples collected for the phytoplankton characterization were stored along a week for sedimentation. After this period the supernatant was decanted, and the pellet was transferred to falcon tubes (with a final volume of 2 mL). The phytoplankton community was identified (Bellinger et al. 1992; Hoppenrath et al., 2009; Kraberg et al., 2010; Baker, 2012; Navarrete et al., 2013) and counted using a Neubauer's chamber in a microscope. Each sample was analysed when at least 800 cells were accounted for, for a total of three replicate for each sampling site. Chlorophyll *a* concentration was determined according to Lorenzen (1967) methodology, and the phytoplankton biomass was calculated after spectrophotometer readings.

The content of organic matter in the sediments was measured in each sediment samples. Each sample was put on an oven (60°C) to dry until constant weight (≈1 week) (dry weight). After this procedure, the sediment samples were burned overnight in a muffle furnace at 450°C and, after cooling, they were weighted (muffle weight). The content of organic matter was determined according to the equation:

$$\text{Organic matter (\%)} = \frac{\text{dry weight} - \text{muffle weight}}{\text{dry weight}} \times 100$$

The sediment samples, after burned in the muffle, were processed to determinate their granulometry. The samples were shacked through a tower of sieves with different size mesh (250µm, 100µm and 50µm) that allowed to differentiate the sediment grain sizes present in each sample. Each fraction retained in each sieve was used to differentiate the samples and determined the type of sediment by comparing with the Udden-Wentworth scale (Wentworth, 1922).

Macroinvertebrates samples were screened with tweezers and the organisms were conserved in ethanol 96%. The identification procedure was conducted in a binocular stereoscope and all organisms were identified up to the species level, whenever possible, using the specific dichotomous identification key of Hayward and Ryland (2017).

Univariate descriptors were calculated:

- abundance, N
- species richness, S
- Margalef index (Margalef, 1958), the index has been introduced to make richness independent of the sample size.

$$d = \frac{(S - 1)}{\ln(N)}$$

- Shannon index,

$$H' = -\sum p_i \log p_i$$

- $H' = -\sum p_i \log_2 p_i$ ($p_i = n_i/N$, with n_i being the i -th taxon abundance; Shannon & Weaver, 1949).

It expresses the "uncertainty" in predicting which species a randomly selected individual belongs to, with values ranging between 0 and ∞ . Like the other diversity indices, it takes into account the richness and distribution of abundances among taxa. A high sample size is assumed ($N \rightarrow \infty$).

- Pielou evenness (Pielou, 1966). It quantifies the evenness in the distribution of abundances between taxa, with values ranging between 0 and 1.

$$J' = \frac{H'}{\log_2(S)}$$

- AMBI biotic index (Borja et al., 2000). Biotic indices are based on the paradigm that the taxonomic composition is affected by the quality of the system, in terms of the quantitative ratio (abundances) between sensitive and tolerant species. However, biotic indices have been also applied to other types of impacts. Calculation steps are the following: 1) taxa are attributed to one of five "ecological groups" describing the taxon sensitivity, based on lists of species (December 2020 version, <https://ambi.azti.es/>; if the taxon is missing, a class has been assigned, when possible, based on expert opinion); 2) a biotic coefficient ranging between 1 and 6 is calculated according to the formula:

$$BC = (0 \times \%GI) + (1.5 \times \%GII) + (3 \times \%GIII) + (4.5 \times \%GIV) + (6 \times \%GV)$$

GI-GV are the percentage abundances of the five ecological groups; 7 is given in case of azoic samples; 3) a discrete biotic index BI 1-7 may be attributed according to reference BC intervals; however, it has not been applied in the present analysis.

- M-AMBI multimetric index (Bald et al., 2005; Muxika et al., 2007). The index integrates S , H' and AMBI through complex multivariate calculations, however it has been demonstrated that it approximates the simple mean of normalised metrics (Sigovini et al. 2013), with 0-1 normalisation calculated over the following

range: a minimum value corresponding to theoretical conditions ($S = 0$, $H' = 0$, $AMBI = 6$) and a maximum value corresponding either to given high-quality reference conditions (which generally differ according to the monitored environment) or to the highest values in the dataset (the lowest in the case of AMBI), the latter being applied in the present analysis (calculated from the whole dataset of marine and lagoon community data). The M-AMBI index therefore assumes values between 0 and 1 (or slightly higher than 1).

Water samples for microplastics characterization were digested (10% potassium hydroxide solution), filtered (GF/C 1.2 μm /pore and $\text{Ø}=47$ mm) and dried (40°C, 48h) according to standardized procedures (Frias et al., 2019, 2022). Several filter blanks were used to evaluate contamination. Each particle was carefully observed in a stereomicroscope with dedicated camera and high-definition pictures were taken. Each particle was identified, digitally measured and sorted by type (fragment, pellet, fiber, film) and colour.

Normality and homogeneity of variance were verified for the obtained data. A one-way ANOVA was performed to compare microplastics size, type and colour among distinct sampling transects. All the statistical analyses were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics Version 27 (IBM®).

6.3 Results

6.3.1 Ave River estuary hydromorphology

The estuary of the Ave River is a small shallow water estuary of 2 km length and between 90 and 120 m-wide, limited by a weir constructed for an historical water mill that prevent the oceanic water going upstream. The bathymetric configuration (Figure 51) revealed a shallow water estuary with mean depths of 4 m (referred to the MSL – Mean Sea Level). The deepest regions, of around 8 m (referred to the MSL), can be found in the upstream estuarine region.

Figure 51 – Bathymetry of the Ave estuary and adjacent coastal region in m (referred to the MSL). Data was acquired in September 2021 in a dedicated campaign under the scope of the MAELSTROM project.

The river flow on the Ave River estuary is low, with an average value of 30 m³/s, maximum values around 60 m³/s and minimum values next to zero (Figure 52a), reflecting the annual precipitation cycle with strong estuarine flows in winter and weaker flows in summer. Extreme river flows can reach 450 m³/s, however, those events are rare (Figure 52b). Notice that the data available only covers a period between 1978 and 2000. Current trends associated, for example, with climate change conditions or with changes in the water use, are not contemplated in this database.

Figure 52 – Ave estuary river flow: a) Monthly mean river flow and maximum and minimum river flow measured for each month; b) Measured river flow. Data was extracted from SNIRH (<https://snirh.apambiente.pt/>) for the last hydrographic basin station available in the water course, and between 1978 and 2000.

The low river flow found in this estuarine region is a clear indicator that the oceanic conditions will be the main drivers of its dynamic. Waves and tides are highly energetic in this area. The waves come mainly from the north-west and west directions, with a mean significant height of 2 m and peak period between 9 s and 13 s. During storminess periods, extremely high energetic conditions are produced on the continental shelf, with normal significant heights between 3 m and 6 m that can

reach 9 m or 12 m (Viitak et al, 2021). However, due to the morphological configuration of the estuary and its breakwaters, it is protected from the waves coming from the ocean. So, the main driver of this estuary is the tide, which, in the NW-Portuguese coast, is mesotidal with a semi-diurnal regime with a 12.4 h-long period (Iglesias et al., 2019). This makes the estuary poorly mixed, presenting strong stratification during mostly part of the year, as clearly demonstrated in the hydrodynamic campaigns performed in the Ave River estuary.

The results of both campaigns were quite similar in terms of vertical structure, due to the existence of low river flows. For both campaigns, the stratification was present, with the less saline river water masses above the saltier oceanic waters (Figure 53 and Figure 54). The freshwater approximately occupies the first meter of the water column, then a shallow mixing layer can be observed, with a strong gradient in all the three measured parameters (salinity, temperature, and pH), followed with the salt/oceanic water at the bottom. The depth of the riverine surface water is maintained along the entire tidal cycle, increasing the depth of the salt water due to the entrance of the salt wedge. In terms of temperature, on October the river showed temperatures around 18 °C, highly influenced by still summer conditions, and temperatures of 16.5 °C was measured for the oceanic water masses. In terms of pH, the freshwater had values of 7.3, meanwhile the oceanic waters presented 6.8. For January, river water masses present temperatures around 11 °C and pH around 7, meanwhile oceanic water masses presented temperatures around 13 °C and pH of 6.4. The pH values measured on the Ave estuary transects are comparable to those found in other estuarine systems from the NW coast of Portugal (e.g. Douro: Iglesias et al., 2020; Minho and Lima: Vieira et al., 2015).

Figure 53 – Vertical profiles of salinity, temperature and pH for the October 2021 campaign during a) low tide conditions and b) high tide conditions.

Figure 54 – Vertical profiles of salinity, temperature and pH for the January 2022 campaign during a) low tide conditions and b) high tide conditions.

Vertical profiles of water velocity along the same transect were also measured and analysed (Figure 55 and Figure 56), presenting generalized low values. For the October campaign, the stronger velocities during flood conditions can be observed in the centre of the channel, with values around 0.6 m/s. During ebb conditions, velocities are mostly negative, with maximum values around 0.6 m/s. The situation for the January campaign is quite similar (Figure 56).

Figure 55 – Vertical velocity profiles along channel in October 2021 campaign for a) mid-flood conditions and b) mid-ebb conditions. Positive velocities (red) are considered from south to north, i.e. entering to the estuary. Black line: Bathymetry. Green line: 94% of the depth. The ADCP measurements between both lines could present some errors due to floor interaction.

Figure 56 – Vertical velocity profiles along channel in January 2022 campaign for a) mid-flood conditions and b) mid-ebb conditions. Positive velocities (red) are considered from south to north, i.e. entering to the estuary. Black line: Bathymetry. Green line: 94% of the depth. The ADCP measurements between both lines could present some errors due to floor interaction.

The strong stratification and the low velocities observed in this estuarine region are indicators of high residence times, which can produce retention of pollutants, microplastics and marine litter inside the estuary during long times, damaging the ecosystem. However, it is worthy to be noticed that no winter conditions associated with strong river flows were captured during the planned campaigns, and the dynamics on the estuary could be different depending on the river flow.

Table 26 showed the characterization of the hydromorphological elements measured in each sampling site and season considering the ecological assessment campaigns (spring 2021, autumn 2021, spring 2022). The Ave River estuary sampling section showed low depths with variation within season. High content of organic matter was recorded, however, with a strong variation between sites. Sediments are characterized by coarse silt to medium sand, and the structure of the margins are distinct (right margin artificial, and the left margin is a wetland). Constant freshwater flow from upstream, increased in rainy periods, is a natural freshwater flow observed in the last section of the Ave River estuary, without exposure to waves resulting from the shape of the estuary inlet (Figure 52, Figure 53, Figure 54 and Table 26).

Table 26 – Results of hydromorphological parameters measured in the 3 sampling sites and the three sampling periods.

Date	Site	Depth (m)	Organic Matter (%)	Hydromorphological elements			Freshwater flow	Exposure to waves
				Granulometry	Intertidal zone structure			
Spring 21	AveR	4.0	13.2±0.36	Coarse Silt	Artificial margin (Wall)	Constant freshwater flow from upstream, with increase in rainy periods	Null	
	AveC	3.6	6.4±0.19	Medium Sand	---			
	AveL	2.0	16.5±0.56	Coarse Silt	Wetland/Artificial margin			
Autumn 21	AveR	5.5	14.4±0.34	Coarse Silt	Artificial margin (Wall)			
	AveC	5.6	11.5±0.49	Coarse Silt/Fine Sand	---			
	AveL	5.6	1.2±0.04	Medium Sand	Wetland/Artificial margin			
Spring 22	AveR	5.2	11.49±2.38	Medium Sand	Artificial margin (Wall)			
	AveC	4.1	11.58±0.52	Coarse Silt	---			
	AveL	3.7	1.05±0.03	Medium Sand	Wetland/Artificial margin			

6.3.2 Physical and chemical characterization

Results were obtained in the three sampling campaigns carried out in spring 2021, autumn 2021 and spring 2022. Table 27 shows the physical and chemical results and the reference values according to WFD for this type of water body. Low values of salinity were recorded; indeed the Ave estuary is classified as A1.1-north strait channel type, oligohaline (<10 salinity). Low values of dissolved oxygen were also recorded, always below of the reference values defined for this water body typology (109 %), however, an excellent ecological quality ratio was achieved. The Ecological Quality Ratio (EQR) is defined as the ratio between the reference value of percentile 90% and the percentile 90% of the samples, and the result achieved is interpreted within a set of boundary values which, in the case of % oxygen, are [0.9-1.1] = excellent; [0.7-0.9[and]1.1-1.2] = good; < 0.7 and > 1.2 = moderate status; (APA, 2021). Regarding nutrient

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concentrations, namely Nitrite+Nitrate, low values recorded showed a final chemical status as good for the three sampling sites in all sampling seasons. High concentrations of ammonia and phosphate were recorded, classified the three sampling sites as a moderate chemical status in all sampling seasons, namely in the autumn season. The boundary values for the EQR result for Nitrite+Nitrate are [0-1[= excellent; [1-2[= good; ≥ 2 moderate status (APA, 2021).

Table 27 – Results of physical and chemical parameters measured in the 3 sampling sites and the three sampling periods, and the chemical status regarding the physical and chemical results. EQR – ecological quality ratio

Date	Site	Secchi (m)	pH	Temp (°C)	Sal	Oxygen (mg/L %)	Nitrites (mg N/L)	Nitrates (mg N/L)	Ammonia (mg N/L)	Phosphate (mg P/L)	
WFD - Reference values					0-10	109	1.00	0.30			
					10-20	109	0.50	0.10			
					20-30	109	0.60	0.40			
					>30	109	0.30	0.20			
Spring 21	Ave R	3.0	7.57	22.6	7.3	8.20	93.8	0.172	1.943	0.053	0.257
	Ave C	3.0	7.44	22.8	6.5	8.21	94.4	0.103	0.949	0.059	0.178
	Ave L	2.0	7.37	23.5	5.2	8.33	97.0	0.121	0.949	0.065	0.205
Autumn 21	Ave R	1.5	9.39	19.8	5.6	8.22	95.2	0.679	0.612	1.679	0.483
	Ave C	2.0	9.45	20.1	5.6	8.08	92.6	0.673	0.474	0.967	0.414
	Ave L	1.4	9.40	20.6	3.9	8.14	95.3	0.968	0.608	0.925	0.372
Spring 22	Ave R	1.5	7.35	16.9	3.0	8.94	91.5	0.842	0.674	0.941	0.138
	Ave C	1.7	7.37	16.9	2.4	8.96	92.1	0.870	0.673	0.993	0.171
	Ave L	1.5	7.43	17.5	1.6	9.10	94.4	0.974	0.673	0.825	0.130
EQR Chemical Status						AveR = 0.87 AveC = 0.86 AveL = 0.89 good	AveR = 1.99 AveC = 1.46 AveL = 1.63 good	AveR = 4.86 AveC = 3.28 AveL = 2.98 moderate	AveR = 3.77 AveC = 3.12 AveL = 2.92 moderate		

Overall, the results obtained for the metals, biotoxins, PAHs and PFAs measured in the water samples showed low values (Table 28, Table 29 and Table 30). Low concentrations of metals were recorded (Table 28) all below of the admissible maximum values according to Law 236/98. At Spring season, concentrations of Cd, Cu and Ni were measured, while in Autumn only Cu values was recorded. No detection levels for biotoxins, PHAs, and PFAs were recorded in the water samples collected along one year (2021) (Table 29 and Table 30), classifying this water body as excellent regarding these compounds.

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Table 28 – Results of the metals measured in the 3 sampling sites and for the three sampling periods, and the chemical status evaluation. AMV – Admissible maximum values.

Date		Cd	Cu	Hg	Ni	Pb	Chemical Status
		(ng/L)	(µg/L)	(µg/L)	(µg/L)	(µg/L)	
	Low236/98 Annex XXI (AMV)	10	100	1	50	50	
	Limit Detection	0.40	0.20	0.40	0.71	0.20	
Spring 21	AveR	1.3 ± 0.2	0.36 ± 0.05	BDL	2.9 ± 0.7	BDL	Good **
	AveC	0.9 ± 0.1	BDL	BDL	3.2 ± 0.2	BDL	
	AveL	2.3 ± 0.1	0.64 ± 0.07	BDL	2.1 ± 0.7	BDL	
Autumn 21	AveR	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	Good **
	AveC	BDL	2.8 ± 0.3	BDL	BDL	BDL	
	AveL	BDL	3.2 ± 1.0	BDL	BDL	BDL	
Spring 22	AveR	ongoing					
	AveC						
	AveL						

** Classification according to national laws, regarding the environmental quality objectives for surface water

Table 29 – Results of biotoxins measured in the 3 sampling sites and for the two sampling periods. AMV – Admissible maximum values.

Date	Anatoxin-a	Cylindrospermopsin	Saxitoxin	Microcystin-LR	Microcystin-RR	Microcystin-YR
Limit Detection	5.7±0.3	3.8±0.7	7.9±1.3	2.9±0.8	4.1±0.3	3.2±0.8
Low236/98 Annex XIII (AMV)	*PSP (paralytic shellfish poisoning) < 80 µg/100 g (of organism); ‡DSP (diarrhoeic shellfish poisoning) absence; †ASP (amnesic shellfish poisoning) < 20 µg/g (of organism);					
Spring 21	AveR	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL
	AveC	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL
	AveL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL
Autumn 21	AveR	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL
	AveC	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL
	AveL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL

Table 30 - Results of PAHs and PFAs for the three sampling sites in Ave estuary and the three sampling periods. AMC - Admissible maximum concentration; BDL - Below detect limit.

Compound	Limit Detection (µg/L)	DL 218/2015 AMC (µg/L)	Spring 21			Autumn 21			
			Ave R	Ave C	Ave L	Ave R	Ave C	Ave L	
Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs)	Naftalen	0.100	130	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL
	Acenaftilen	0.010		BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL
	Acenafteno	0.010		BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL
	Fluoreno	0.020		BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL
	Fenantreno	0.030		BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL
	Antraceno	0.020	0.1	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL
	Fluoranteno	0.030	0.12	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL
	Pireno	0.060		BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL
	Benzo(a)antrace no	0.010		BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL
	Criseno	0.010		BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL
	Benzo[b]fluorant eno	0.020	0.017	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL
	Benzo[k]fluorant eno	0.020	0.017	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL
	Benzo(a)pireno	0.020	0.027	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL
	Indeno[1,2,3 - cd]pireno	0.020		BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL
	Benzo[ghi]perilen o	0.020	8.2x10 ⁻⁴	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL
	Dibenzo(a,h)antr aceno	0.010		BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL
Perfluoroalkyl and Polyfluoroalkyl Substances (PFAs)	PFBA	0.010		BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL
	PFPeA	0.010		BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL
	PFHxA	0.010		BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL
	PFHpA	0.010		BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL
	PFOA	0.010		BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL
	PFNA	0.010		BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL
	PFDA	0.010		BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL
	PFUnDA	0.010		BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL
	PFDoDA	0.010		BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL
	PFHxS	0.010		BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL
	PFHpS	0.010		BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL
	PFOS	0.010		BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL
	PFDS	0.010		BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL
	FOSA	0.010		BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL
	6:2 FTS	0.010		BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL
8:2 FTS	0.010		BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	

6.3.3 Biological elements

The results of the two biological elements analyzed are presented in Table 31 and Figure 57. Overall, the macroinvertebrates communities showed a low abundance, richness, and diversity values. Indeed, these low values do not allow computing AMBI (AZTI's Marine Biotic Index) and BAT (Benthic Assessment Tool) indexes to achieve the

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ecosystem status classification for the aquatic ecosystem. Regarding the phytoplankton evaluation, low chlorophyll *a* concentration was observed for all sites and sampling periods. Despite the reduced number of values still available, the 90% percentile was calculated by integrating all values. This allowed to have a reliable assessment of the Ave Estuary as a good ecological status regarding only the phytoplankton element (Ecological Quality Ratio = 90% percentile reference value (6.67)/90% percentile of the samples). The boundary values for the EQR result for Chlorophyll *a* are > 0.670 = excellent; [0.47-0.67] = good; [0.30-0.47] = moderate status; [0.20-0.3] = bad; < 0.2 poor status (APA, 2021). However, the values obtained so far revealed a bad ecological status considering the macroinvertebrates, in agreement with the ecological status achieved in the 3^o cycle of monitoring program – bad (2021-2027) (Figure 45).

Table 31- Biological parameters results (benthic macroinvertebrates and phytoplankton) measured in the 3 sampling sites and the three sampling periods, and the ecological status evaluation.

		Biological elements						Ecological Status
		Macroinvertebrates			Phytoplankton			
Date		Abundance	Margalef (d)	Diversity Index (Shannon Wiener - H')	AM BI	BAT	Chlorophyll <i>a</i> (µg/L)	Percentile 90%
WFD reference values			1.9	2.30	2.50			6.67 µg/L
Spring 21	AveR	28					3.84±0.35*	excellent
	AveC	18	0.80	0.15			4.18±0.35*	
	AveL	1					5.41±0.36*	
Autumn 21	AveR	1					3.94±0.38*	
	AveC	0					4.31±0.38*	
	AveL	197	1.74	0.35			5.66±0.39*	
Spring 22	AveR						1.65±0.75*	
	AveC	ongoing					1.45±0.19*	
	AveL						1.30±0.33*	

Ave estuary – A1.1 – north strait channel type, oligohaline (<10 salinity); *individual values

Stations	AMBI	Diversity	Richness	X	Y	Z	M-AMBI	Status
BAD	6	0	0	-2.58	-1.38	0.01	0.00	Bad
HIGH	3.47	2.06	8	2.15	1.56	-0.00	1.00	High
Spr 21	6.000	0.34	2	-1.69	-1.14	-0.00	0.16	Bad
Aut 21	3.470	1.16	5	0.43	1.10	-0.00	0.69	Good
Spr 22	5.883	2.06	8	1.69	-0.15	-0.00	0.77	Good

A)

B)

Figure 57 – A) Summary table of AMBI software results; B) Figure of the ecosystems disturbance classification according to AMBI results.

6.3.4 Macro litter and microplastics

Visual monitoring results indicated that the Ave River estuary has considerable contamination by macrolitter (e.g. styrofoam, bags, plastic bottles – Figure 58), denoting a prevalence of land-based public litter sources, with an estimated frequency of 19.1 and 16.3 floating items per hour, measured during Spring 2021 and Autumn 2021 campaigns, respectively.

Figure 58 – Percentage of the top six macro litter items identified in the Ave estuary.

The most percentage (aprox. 99%) of micro plastic particles collected had sizes lower than 5 mm, considered microplastics, being more than 40% between 0.100 and 0.500 μm (Figure 59a). The predominant microplastics colour was blue (Figure 59b), in good agreement with other studies (Montoto-Martínez et al., 2021), being also the predominant colour of microplastics found in marine and estuarine biota (Ugwu et al., 2021). The analysed samples also showed a predominance of microfibers and plastic fragments (Figure 59c and Figure 61). Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) among all microplastics sizes and types among distinct sampling transects were found (Figure 60 a, c). In addition, significant differences ($p < 0.05$) among blue, transparent, red, white, black and green microplastics were observed among sampled sites (Figure 60 b).

Several published research works highlighted the distinct relationship between microfibers in historical seawater samples and the volume of synthetic fibers production (Thompson et al. 2004; Henry et al., 2019). Fibers are widely produced and used for several purposes (e.g. textiles, ropes), and can enter into the environment during their production, use and disposal (Hernandez et al., 2017). It was suggested that around 0.19 million tons of fibers, only from synthetic textiles, enter into the marine environment each year (Henry et al., 2019). Fishing gears and other materials using in marine fishery may also release fibers into the seawater and sediments (Andrady et al., 2011).

Figure 59 – Percentages of microplastics collected per a) size class, b) colour, and c) type.

Figure 60 – Percentage of anthropogenic particles recovered from each sampled Transect (T1-T5 (3a), per a) size class, b) colour, and c) type.

Figure 61 – Examples of found microplastics: a) Fibers; b) Fragments; c) Films; d) Pellets.

6.4 Conclusions

Regarding the results obtained for the ecological assessment of the Ave River estuary, this water body can be classified as moderate to poor according to the assessment of nutrients and the biological element benthic macroinvertebrates, respectively. The analysis of the hydro-morphodynamic conditions revealed a shallow depth high stratified estuary, mainly driven by the tide due to the low river flows and presenting low current velocities. Furthermore, both macro litter and microplastics identified in the same area highlighted major concerns on potential impacts on both ecosystem and human health. Considering the prevalence of microplastics between 0.100 and 0.500 μm , this class size can be bioavailable, via active or passive ingestion, to a wide range of organisms as they overlap with the size range of their prey, including zooplankton and ichthyoplankton, with potential transfer up the higher trophic levels, including seafood. The results obtained so far highlight the urgent need for more temporal and spatial monitoring of plastic pollution in estuaries and other coastal ecosystems. This scientific knowledge is essential for adequate public engagement and political commitment, working together on more effective management of litter and marine and coastal ecosystems. The here-obtained results showed the urgent necessity to developed restoration measures to meet the WFD objectives, where all aquatic ecosystems achieve good ecological status.

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ANNEXES

